

**UNIVERSITY OF GLOBAL HEALTH EQUITY JUNIOR SURGICAL CLERKSHIP
(SURGERY 301), JANUARY TO JUNE, 2022:
REVIEW OF SURGICAL CURRICULUM DELIVERY**

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Executive Summary

The 11 week University of Global Health Equity (UGHE) Junior Surgical clerkship ran in two cohorts from January through June 2022.

- **Program coordination partners:** Butaro District Hospital (BDH), Partners in Health (PIH), the Harvard Program in Global Surgery (PGSSC)
- **Activities:** Clinical rotations at BDH, evening clinical call duty, 74 in-class and simulation sessions
- **Faculty:** 30 faculty and fellows from local and international institutions. On average, 68% were visiting faculty and 38% were physically present. There was one core BDH surgeon involved.

Summary of Learning

Most expectations for learning were largely achieved (15/21; 71%). This included activities related to patient intake, the formation of appropriate diagnoses and plans of investigation, triage, patient management of specific medical presentations, and overall professionalism. The remaining benchmarks (29%) that were considered 'borderline' between achieved and not-achieved were limited by the lack of student permissions to practice patient record documentation and limited patient volumes for the practice of specific case evaluation and management.

Student Assessments of the Clerkship (n=30)

- The program was rated 'excellent' or 'very good' by 67% (20/30) and 'fair' by 30% (9/30).
- They approved of current faculty and thought simulations were a highlight in their education
- Less than 50% of students (13/30) agreed that the curriculum should be delivered solely at BDH. This was primarily due to the inadequate patient case volume in the OR.

Hospital Staff Survey (n=19)

- Staff would welcome medical students back to BDH for future surgical clerkships. The majority (95%), rated the junior surgical clerkship as either 'excellent', 'very good', or 'good'.
- In contrast to the students, 100% and 95% of staff believed that patient volume and variety at BDH was sufficient for the students' learning needs.
- Staff felt they were qualified to teach medical students and had time to devote to teaching. They had a positive relationship with UGHE faculty but wished for improvement in communication regarding both student and staff expectations.

Key Recommendations for BDH Partnership

1. Increase the number/specialties of BDH surgeons and adjust General Practitioner's schedule to facilitate their involvement in the clerkship delivery.
2. Complete the expansion of infrastructure and space, including surgical bedspace.
3. Adjust outpatient department flow to allow student access to surgical patients prior to referral.
4. Address supply chain challenges (medication, disposables, etc.).
5. Lead a system-wide surgical quality improvement initiative in partnership with UGHE to identify system challenges and proffer potential solutions.

Key Recommendations for UGHE

1. *To improve student exposure:* Consider use of additional or alternative clerkship sites, continue to utilize simulation, and explore virtual reality/telesurgery options
2. *To ensure clinical activity is maximized:* Improve facilitation of visiting surgeon licenses, adjust didactic schedule to ensure Wednesdays are clinical, and improve logbook feedback consistency
3. *To improve teaching and mentorship:* Enhance clarity of student and BDH staff and increase number of UGHE preceptors (possibly GPs) to permit full accompaniment through the clinical day

Extended Summary

1.0 Introduction

The first 11 week University of Global Health Equity (UGHE) Junior Surgical clerkship started on Monday, 10th January, 2022 and ended on Friday, 25 March, 2022. The second cohort started on Monday, 28 March, 2022 and ended on Friday, 17 June, 2022. Thirty students in total rotated on the surgical ward, operating room, the recovery room, and the accident and emergency of Butaro District Hospital (BDH), and had in-class and simulation engagements on the UGHE Butaro Campus. A total of 74 in-class and simulation sessions were facilitated within each 11 week rotation ranging from didactic in-person or virtual lectures, flipped classroom sessions, student and faculty-led seminars, simulation sessions, and tutorial sessions. The entire first week of the rotation was dedicated to simulation training on the basics of surgery, mid-posting evaluations were held in the fifth week, while the final week was a summative evaluation week.

This inaugural surgical clerkship resulted from multiple partnerships. Notably, UGHE worked closely with the Butaro District Hospital, a 150-bed hospital supported by Partners In Health located adjacent to the UGHE campus in Burera district, and with the Harvard Program in Global Surgery and Social Change (PGSSC) to lead the design and coordinate the delivery of the curriculum.

2.0 Clerkship faculty

Thirty faculty and fellows who worked to deliver the didactic and clinical curriculum from UGHE, BDH, PGSSC, the University of Rwanda, Creighton fellowships, Rwanda Military Hospital, CHUB, Leipzig University, Brigham and Women's Hospital simulation center, Globalsurg box teams, Jos University Teaching Hospital, and University of California, San Francisco, and King Faisal Hospital among others.

Up to 71.4% (n=15) and 65.2% (n=15) of faculty were visiting faculty for the first and second cohorts respectively. Of 32 facilitators involved in curriculum delivery, 12 (37.5%) were physically present with the students for all or part of their teaching and training engagements. Up to 18.5% of facilitators were consistently present at UGHE throughout the inaugural surgery rotation. Only five of the faculty were engaged in clinical surgical service delivery at Butaro District Hospital across both cohorts, and of these 1 was a BDH surgeon.

3.0 Summary of Activities

Sessions	Week Day	MONDAY	TUESDAY	WEDNESDAY	THURSDAY	FRIDAY
Morning Clinical Sessions (7:30am-3:30pm)	7:30-8:30am	Morning Meetings	Morning Meetings		Morning Meetings	Morning Meetings
		Ward/OPD/OR/Anesthesia/Emergency	Ward/OPD/OR/Anesthesia/Emergency	Lecture (8:15-9:45am)	Ward/OPD/OR/Anesthesia/Emergency	Ward/OPD/OR/Anesthesia/Emergency
		Ward/OPD/OR/Anesthesia/Emergency	Ward/OPD/OR/Anesthesia/Emergency	CBCL/Lectures (10:00-12:00pm)	Lectures/CBCL/Flipped Class/Seminar (2-4pm)	Simulation (11:00-1:30pm)
Afternoon Lectures (4:00-5:00pm)		Lectures /Flipped Class/Seminar	Lectures /Flipped Class/Seminar	Lectures / Flipped Class/ Seminar	Lectures / Flipped Class/ Seminar	
Clinical Call Duty (7:00-10:00pm)		ON CALL	ON CALL	ON CALL	ON CALL	ON CALL

Following an introductory simulation heavy week, daily activities for the next 10 clinical weeks began with a morning report at the hospital from 7:30am and ended after 5:00pm following a 1 hour didactic engagement. On Wednesdays students were fully on campus, while Friday contacts ended at 1:30pm. Each student had clinical call duty for 3 hours a night each week. Students were divided into subgroups and rotated through the Surgical Ward/Operating Room, the Surgical Ward/Out-patient Department, and the Emergency Room/Anesthesia (including the plaster of paris application service and recovery room).

4.0 Summary of Learning

A daily clinical morning report held at BDH on Monday, Tuesday, Thursday and Friday which involved presentation of surgical cases encountered during the previous call duty. Pre-rounds and clinical ward work followed including clerking of new patients, updates on inpatients, wound care, surgical drain maintenance, vital signs, and bedside surgery. These were followed by bedside teachings, with student presentations, bedside tutorials, and teaching rounds. Structured learning in classrooms covered ten thematic areas over 10 weeks. The ratio of virtual to in-person didactics was about 3:1. Didactics included traditional lectures and flipped classrooms, case-based clinical learning sessions, simulation-based learning for both procedures and scenarios, student-led seminars, and faculty-led seminars. All sessions were covered appropriately, but the order of lectures was frequently adjusted to accommodate the visiting faculties clinical engagements for both cohorts. Expectations for learning and faculty assessments of the extent to which these expectations were achieved as a whole following delivery of the curriculum are as shown below.

Expectation for Junior Surgery Clerkship	Entrustable Professional Activity	Achieved / Borderline / Not-achieved
Execution with reactive supervision, i.e., on request and quickly available	Document a clinical encounter in the patient record	Borderline-theoretically achieved (limited permissions to documenting in patient records)
	Provide an oral presentation of a clinical encounter	Achieved
	Form clinical questions and retrieve evidence to advance patient care	Achieved
Execution with direct, proactive supervision	Gather a history and perform a physical exam adapted to the patient's clinical situation	Achieved
	Formulate and justify prioritized differential diagnosis following a clinical encounter.	Achieved
	Formulate an initial plan of investigation based on the diagnostic hypotheses	Achieved
	Recommend and interpret common diagnostic screening tests	Achieved
	Give or receive a patient handover to transition care responsibility (particularly refer a patient appropriately and adequately prepare the patient for transfer)	Borderline (limited permissions to documenting in patient records)
	Recognize a patient requiring urgent or emergency surgical care and initiate evaluation and management	Achieved
	Obtain informed consent for tests and/or procedures	Achieved
	Educate patients on surgical disease management, health promotion and preventive medicine	Achieved
	Perform general physician procedures relevant to surgery (NG tube, venipuncture, catheterization)	Achieved

	Evaluate and manage a patient with an inguinal hernia	Borderline- (Non-operative/theoretical component achieved, operative components deficient- poor case volume and case mix at BDH)* Only 6 herniorrhaphies were performed during student hours across both cohorts
	Evaluate and manage a patient with right lower quadrant pain	Borderline- (Non-operative component achieved, operative component deficient-poor case volume and case mix at BDH) * No appendicectomies were performed during student hours across both cohort
	Evaluation and initial management of a patient presenting with trauma	Achieved (simulation enhanced)
	Perform other consensus minor to intermediate clinical surgical procedures (See Delphi result list e.g. excision of lumps, bumps, debridement, drain removal))	Borderline (poor case volume and case mix at BDH)
	Recognize and initiate referral and transfer of surgical patients beyond the capacity of the district hospital's scope of care	Achieved
Observation but no execution by the trainee, even with direct supervision	Formulate, communicate, and implement surgical management plans	Achieved
	Collaborate as member of an interprofessional team	Achieved
	Identify system failures and contribute to a culture of safety and improvement (participate in surgical health quality improvement initiatives e.g., surgical checklist)	Achieved
	[Observe] other consensus major clinical surgical procedures (See Delphi result list)	Not achieved (poor case volume and case mix at BDH) *X% of all general surgery cases were breast surgeries

5.0 Student evaluations

Faculty employed both formative (40%) and summative (60%) components to assess students.

Assessment	Description	Contribution to Final Grade
Formative Assessments	Faculty evaluations	10%
	Logbook reviews	10%
	Clinical case reports	10%
	Assignments	10%
Summative Assessments	Mid-attachment Objective Structured Clinical Examination	20%
	2. End Module Multiple Choice Questions	20%
	3. Summative OSCE	20%
TOTAL		100%

6.0 Student performance

For both cohorts, students performed satisfactorily (with scores ranging from 66.68- 86.99%). Final grades included 6 As, 15 B+s, 8 Bs, and only 1 C+. There was no statistically significant difference in the average scores between the cohorts, however average performance of the second cohort was lower (cohort 1 score- 82%; cohort 2- 79%). This may reflect the increasing hospital supply chain challenges, suspension of elective surgeries, breaks in continuity of learning during frequent public holidays within the second rotation (combined 11 days). There is also the possibility of burnout following several months of an intense inaugural clinical clerkship.

7.0 Clerkship Assessments

Assessment of the clerkship was carried out using mixed methods, with responses from students and hospital staff.

7.1 Student survey summary

The program was rated as either 'excellent' or 'very good' by 66.7% (20/30), and as satisfactory (fair) by 30% (9/30). Up to 90% of respondents agreed that the clerkship should continue to be led by current faculty. In contrast, less than 50% of students (13/30) agreed that the curriculum should continue to be delivered at BDH.

Students stated that surgical patient case volume was 'excellent' or 'good' in the outpatient clinic (26/30, 86.7%), but largely inadequate in the OR (20/30, 66% 'unsatisfactory' or just 'satisfactory'), and borderline on the wards and emergency department. Perceptions of surgical case mix were similar, with highest case diversity in the surgical OPD, but least case diverse in the operating room.

Students largely felt that they were best able to contribute to patient care on the surgical ward (24/30; 80%), and a majority (23/30, 76.7%) felt the ward provided 'good' or 'excellent' opportunities to present cases and perform care. This was in contrast with the OR, where only 56.7% (17/30) felt able to contribute positively to patient care. Only 20% (6/30) were of the opinion that the OR provided 'good' or 'excellent' opportunities to perform or assist in surgeries.

From a survey limited to the first cohort, most (75%) felt pre-class readings were appropriate, in-class teaching was adequate (87.5%), and strongly agreed that in-class powerpoints were appropriate in content and design (62.5%). Simulation was noted as a strong point of the posting, with most strongly agreeing (62.5%) or agreeing (25%) that it was useful to achieving the course objectives. Only 1 student used a recommended textbook regularly (at least weekly) during the posting. The rest depended on pre-readings, in-class materials, and online internet resources more consistently.

7.2 Hospital staff survey summary

Nineteen BDH clinicians who had interacted with students and facilitated the clinical posting in a variety of roles- including a surgeon, medical officers and interns, ward nurses, OR nurses, emergency department nurses, and non-physician anesthetists- were surveyed. Irrespective of their role, the staff overwhelmingly agreed that they would welcome medical students back to BDH for future surgical clerkships, and the majority (94.7%, 18/19) rated the junior surgical clerkship as either 'excellent', 'very good', or 'good'. Most BDH staff (63.2 %, 12/19) agreed that students contributed positively to patient care in the hospital during their surgical clerkship. In contrast to the predominant opinion of the student body, however, staff unanimously believed that patient volume (100%) and variety (94.7%, 18/19) at BDH was sufficient for the students' learning needs.

Staff felt generally well equipped to teach the students, agreeing that they felt qualified to teach medical students (14/19; 73.7%) and that they had enough time to devote to teaching (16/19; 84.2%). However, 42.1% (8/19) of the staff disagreed that workforce capacity was sufficient for teaching and training. The majority had a positive relationship with UGHE faculty; most (94.7%, 18/19) 'strongly agreed' that the faculty were helpful with teaching, however, 26.3% (5/19) felt there was room for improvement in communication with UGHE faculty.

7.3 Student focus groups, and qualitative survey components

Triangulating qualitative evidence from 5 student focus groups and qualitative components of both student and staff surveys, barriers to and enhancers of an effective Junior Surgical Clerkship were identified. These are as shown below.

Themes	Barriers to effectiveness of the clerkship	Enhancers of the effectiveness of the clerkship
Teaching and learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Limited faculty supervision - The objectives were not clear to students and BDH staff - BDH staff did not know the level of knowledge of the students - The staff have a high workload - Too many students in the OR and the ward. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Visiting faculty were very resourceful - Dr M [BDH specialist surgeon] is a good educator and is motivated to teach. - BDH staff are eager to teach - There is a good relationship between the UGHE staff and BDH staff - The students have a professional relationship with BDH staff - Shortage of staff gives students room for more involvement.
Patient care	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - BDH is short staffed - In particular there are few physician specialists at BDH - Wards are not multidisciplinary - The hospital often encounters supply chain issues - BDH as a district hospital isn't set up to effectively assess and manage patients with trauma - Few laboratory investigations are done at BDH or if performed are often reported late - Accommodating students potentially places further strain on the system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Because of workforce shortages, there is greater scope for students to be engaged in patient care - Support provided by PIH - The patients are given food - BDH has good hygiene practices - BDH is working toward becoming a teaching hospital
Clinical exposure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Low volume and variety of surgical cases - Surgeries were canceled or delayed due to resources limitations and supply chain issues - Difficulties in following up a patient throughout their hospital stay due to students having to rotate through different clinical areas - Interesting cases are often referred to other referral hospitals - There is only one surgeon and two ORs (with one reserved for obstetrics and gynecology cases) - Some examples of poor teamwork between BDH staff were highlighted - Availability of hospital scrubs was limited, affecting students ability to assist or observe surgeries 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The students were motivated to learn - The hospital is expanding, so there is more room for teaching - Good volume of minor procedures
Work support and clerkship organization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Some BDH staff reacted badly when approached by students - Students' interventions and input were sometimes not considered during ward rounds - Initially, some staff were reluctant to teach the students - Students missed some lectures while they were in the OR - There was no formalized clinical teaching program in the afternoon - Lack of on-site study space for students 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Most staff are very supportive - Most faculty members were eager to teach and answer students' questions - There are young GPs at BDH who are very eager to teach the students

8.0 Clerkship SWOT Analysis

A summary Strength, Weakness, Opportunities and Threats analysis is presented in the image below.

9.0 Challenges and Proposed Solutions

In this assessment, we have identified challenges and possible solutions to these challenges. The table below summarizes these.

Challenges	Proposed solutions
Challenges on Hospital-level organization/Number of Specialists	
Bed space for surgical patients is severely limited, and this limits the number of surgeries possible. This has a limiting effect on the volume of patients that students can interact with.	Expansion of hospital surgical bedspace.
The presence of only 1 hospital General Surgeon is a capacity limitation to both teaching and surgical service provision.	Support from our visiting faculty has given a positive boost to helping expand services to some degree, but the presence of an additional surgeon will be essential support to service expansion.
Insufficient surgical providers posted to the surgical	Encourage hire of surgical faculty, and trained

ward.	perioperative/ surgical nurses
Relatively high turnover of general practitioners and surgical nurses	Encourage stability by maintaining dedicated GPs on the surgery service
Limitation in OR space (only 1 staffed OR available for surgery; second OR is maintained for Obstetrics and Gynecology)	Infrastructural expansion with inclusion of more ORs so as to create space for visiting surgeons and fellows to operate. This will reduce patient wait times and clear up the backlog of patients on the surgery waiting list.
Low volume and variety of surgical cases coupled with significant case delays and cancellations due to resource limitations and supply chain challenges	Mitigation of supply chain challenges at a hospital administration level. Deliberate patient selection for non-breast oncologic surgeries, and expansion of OR space. The backlog of cases potentially guarantees good volume, but facility limitations have to be addressed to permit sufficient diverse case mix and sufficient case volumes.
Limited portfolio of investigations	Prioritize additions of culture and sensitivity and CT scans to BDH investigation portfolio. Public-private partnership might be a consideration.
Delays in receiving investigation results as a barrier to care and learning	Consider a time limit policy for receiving patient results.
Direct referral from the general OPD of surgical patients before contact with surgery students-interesting and unique cases are often referred to other (referral) hospitals.	Streamline the OPD to ensure that surgical teams and students see the patients prior to transfer without increasing the patient wait times.
Lack of study space for students within the hospital	Create a dedicated student study space within BDH for learners, like a medical student library in partnership with UGHE.
No dedicated space for student clerking at the OPD- only 1 room available.	Identify or create space for students to clerk patients and assist with surgical patient evaluation. This will increase the speed of patient encounters (by ensuring that new patients history and examinations are performed prior to seeing the specialist)
Challenges in Hospital Facilitator Training	
Clerkship objectives were unclear to students and BDH staff	Create additional avenues for facilitator training.
BDH staff did not know the baseline level of knowledge of the students	BDH facilitator pre-clerkship training with translation into kinyarwanda (involving ward assistants, nurses, GPs, anesthesiologists and perioperative nurses).
Initial reluctance of certain staff to teach students.	Training of trainers
Challenges in UGHE Surgery Departmental Level Organization	
Limited faculty supervision	
Clerkship objectives were unclear to students	Improve pre-clerkship orientation- emphasizing competencies and objectives of clinical time at BDH. Reinforce this throughout the posting with a 2-weekly session

Clerkship objectives were unclear to BDH staff	Involve all cadres of BDH staff (nurses, support staff and anaesthesiologists)
Extended didactic/flipped classroom interactions beyond 5pm	Lecture start and stop times should be respected by faculty and visiting faculty
Inadequate number of hospital scrubs affecting students ability to assist or observe surgeries	Ensure the purchase of UGHE student scrubs, gowns, and clogs to reduce the burden on BDH resources.
Wednesday as a non-clinical day despite significant OR opportunities	Move non-clinical day to Friday
Absence of a formalized clinical teaching program in the afternoons	Move some clinical teaching to afternoons.
Student Level Challenges	
Poor timeliness of students	Include timeliness into the clerkship grading beyond faculty assessment. Repeated training on professionalism.
Lack of learner independence	Incorporate emphasis on the dynamics of clinical learning, methods of self-directed learning, and the difference between pre-clinical and clinical learning into the Introduction to Clinical Practice. Encourage learner independence to an appropriate degree. This may be handled with time, experience and exposure.
Students missed some lectures while they were in the OR	Ensure that students prioritize clinical engagements over didactics. Clerkship administrative teams should ensure lectures are recorded and posted on Canvas for learners.

10.0 Conclusion

The clerkship was successfully concluded, the learning objectives were largely attained. A number of challenges were encountered, but possible solutions are suggested in hope that future cohort's learning experience will improve. Most students do not advise that the clerkship is continued at BDH because of low surgical volume and inadequate case mix, but this can be addressed by expanding the clerkship to additional sites and strengthening the surgical workforce (numbers and expertise) at the hospital.

10.1 Summary of Recommendations for BDH Partnership

- Continue the transformation of BDH into a teaching hospital
- Increase the number and specialities of BDH surgeons.
- Complete the much needed expansion of infrastructure and space (with specific reference to the Operating rooms, surgical wards and the surgery outpatient departments) to accommodate an increasing number of students.
- Expand the surgical bedspace at BDH
- Adjust outpatient department clinical flow, such that surgery students have access to all surgical patients prior to referral.
- Adjust the GP schedule to facilitate presence and continuity on the surgical wards; the presence of 3 dedicated GPs in the surgical service would strengthen accompaniment significantly.
- Address supply chain challenges (medication, disposables etc)

- Lead a system-wide surgical quality improvement initiative in partnership with UGHE to identify system challenges and proffer potential solutions.

10.2 Summary of Recommendations for UGHE

- Consider use of additional or alternative clerkship sites to improve student exposure to a larger variety and higher volume of surgeries. This could be in the form of referral hospitals or complementary district hospitals with emphasis on trauma, gastrointestinal care etc.
- Adjust surgery schedule to free up Wednesday mornings for clinical activity
- Ensure logbooks are submitted 2-weekly to permit consistent formative feedback
- Enhance clarity of student and BDH staff expectations through pre-clerkship training workshops and continuous engagements
- Repeatedly emphasize the value of reading of course details (syllabus) iteratively to learners
- Emphasize the use of textbooks as reference at the start of the clerkship.
- Improve facilitation of visiting surgeon licenses to ensure that clinical activity is maximized to support the attending surgeon.
- Increase number of UGHE preceptors (possibly GPs) to permit full accompaniment through the clinical day
- Continue to lean on simulation and explore virtual reality/telesurgery options to increase student exposures to local, regional and international surgeries
- Introduce an emphasis on student-led learning and professionalism (including timeliness) into the Introduction to Practice of Medicine course

**UNIVERSITY OF GLOBAL HEALTH EQUITY JUNIOR SURGICAL CLERKSHIP
(SURGERY 301), JANUARY TO JUNE, 2022:
REVIEW OF SURGICAL CURRICULUM DELIVERY**

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Timely access to safe and affordable surgery is not equitably realized globally with over 5 billion people unable to access such care. This shortfall in the provision of surgical care is most pronounced in Low- and Middle-Income Countries (LMICs) where almost 95% receive inadequate quality surgical care¹. Ensuring that countries have a suitable specialist surgical, anesthetic, and obstetric (SAO) provider density is an important component of achieving universal access to surgical care. A target of 20 surgical providers per 100,000 population has been identified as one of six important indicators for achieving adequate surgical access at country levels. Many countries in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) fall short of this benchmark. Rwanda for example, had an SAO specialist provider density of just 1 per 100, 000 as of 2017 and this shortage is even greater in rural areas². As at 2017, only 9 surgeons, 2 obstetricians, and 14 anaesthesiologists provided care for rural Rwandan populations at district level hospitals².

Several innovative training approaches have been suggested to address the shortage of healthcare providers in SSA, however, education and training is an important cornerstone of all attempts at increasing surgical workforce capacity. Focusing undergraduate medical education and training in rural centers has been suggested as one key strategy to addressing issues of surgical access^{3,4}. Traditional training centers in SSA are housed in tertiary hospitals which are hubs of residency and specialist practice. The large number of trainees and hierarchical design implies reduced hands-on clinical practice for more junior learners and medical students. (ref) Rural district hospitals present the potential of practical clinical exposure and of a good learning environment that allows students to familiarize themselves with diseases that are common in the community but are not referred to urban, tertiary hospitals. In addition, as most students will initially practice within district hospital settings, rurally-based programs allow students to become acquainted with nuances of the practice environment, and local cultures relevant to the communities in which they are training and will be practicing on graduation. Interest in surgical care careers has been noted when students have non-metropolitan clerkships⁵. Furthermore, there is also evidence of increased retention rates of medical doctors in rural areas for medical students trained in rural hospitals⁶⁻⁹.

The University of Global Health Equity (UGHE) is a new health sciences university, founded in 2018, located in rural northern Rwanda. It aims to provide locally-driven and contextually-relevant medical education in an attempt to improve access to high-quality healthcare in the most marginalized rural communities.(ref)UGHE currently runs two flagship programs: a one-year Masters in Science of Global Health Delivery and a 6-year Bachelor of Medicine, Bachelor of Surgery (MBBS) undergraduate degree program. The inaugural MBBS class of 2025 commenced their first clinical clerkships in January 2022 based at Butaro District Hospital (BDH) which is a 150-bed Partners In Health funded hospital located adjacent to the UGHE campus in Burera district.

UGHE students come into medical training with a voluntary commitment (*Umusanzi*) to practice in rural environments for 5 years following their medical education. As surgical care will be a core part of their practice, the curriculum focuses on ensuring their proficiency in basic surgery (Bellwether procedures) and ability to stabilize and transfer emergencies that are beyond the capacity of a district hospital. To ensure delivery of a contextually-relevant curriculum, the Department of Surgery at UGHE undertook a modified Delphi consensus exercise from June through November 2021 to identify essential topics and procedures that undergraduate medical students should be exposed to during medical school in order to

equip them for providing surgical care to rural population in Rwanda and more broadly SSA¹⁰. The results from this Delphi consensus were then utilized to guide curriculum development and delivery of the junior and senior surgical clerkships at UGHE¹⁰.

This report presents the results of our review process following completion of the first iteration of the junior surgical clerkship (Surgery 301).

2.0 OVERARCHING OBJECTIVE

The overarching objective of this quality improvement project is to review Surgery 301 curriculum delivery for the MBBS class of 2025 and suggest iterative improvement. Learnings from this review will be used to guide adaptations of the program for future MBBS classes and form a foundation for the design and delivery of the senior surgery clerkship.

2.1 Specific aims

The specific aims of this review report is as follows:

1. To describe in detail the MBBS class of 2025 junior surgery curriculum delivery.
2. To identify barriers and enhancers to junior surgery curriculum delivery using a mixed methods approach.
3. To review and describe surgical volume and surgery case-mix at BDH during the junior surgery clerkship period (January 10th 2022 through June 17th 2022).
 - a. Correlation of surgical volume and surgical case-mix to student exposure.
 - b. Review of case delays and surgical cancellations with root cause analysis over a two month period (21st April 2022 through 17th June 2022) during the junior surgery clerkship.
4. To provide recommendations for implementation of subsequent iterations of surgical, and other clinical curricula at UGHE.
5. To recommend a generic framework for implementing clinical surgery curriculum delivery at the district hospital level.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

Our methodology consisted of 3 broad approaches.

1. A desk review of UGHE surgical clerkship syllabus, documentation, training material, lectures, grading, examination formats, and other curriculum delivery logistics using a narrative synthesis.
2. Assessment of barriers and enhancers to curriculum deliver using mixed methods
 - a. Quantitative, paper-based survey of all medical students completing the junior surgical clerkship from 10th January - 17th June 2022
 - b. Qualitative, paper-based survey of all medical students completing the junior surgical clerkship from 10th January - 17th June 2022
 - c. Five in-person focus group discussions with all medical students completing the junior surgical clerkship from 10th January - 17th June 2022
 - d. Quantitative survey of BDH staff at active training points (Emergency Department, Operating Room, Surgical Wards, Recovery Room, and Surgery Out-patient Department) who participated in delivery of clinical training for the junior surgical clerkship from 10th January - 17th June 2022
 - e. Qualitative paper-based survey of BDH staff at active training points (Emergency Department, Operating Room, Surgical Wards, and Recovery Room) who participated in delivery of clinical training for the junior surgical clerkship from 10th January - 17th June 2022
3. Quantitative audit of surgical volume and case mix through review of

- a. Butaro District Hospital operative log from 10th January - 17th June 2022 inclusive (covering the duration of the junior surgical clerkship)
- b. Student logbooks, completed by each individual students during completion of their surgical clerkships

4.0 RESULTS

4.1.1 Curriculum delivery

4.1.1.1 Clerkship leadership, faculty, and staff engagements

The MBBS Junior Surgical Clerkship (Surg 301) was directed by Professor Robert Riviello, Head of Surgery, and coordinated by Dr Barnabas Alayande, with support from Dr Callum Forbes, an anesthesiologist and Global Surgery fellow. Secretarial and logistics support was provided by Dr Jules Iradukunda. Close supervision was provided by Dr Natalie McCall, Head of the Clinical Division, and Professor Abebe Bekele, Dean of Medicine and Deputy Vice Chancellor, Research and Academic affairs.. Appendix 1 is a list of instructional staff involved in curriculum delivery. Up to 71.4% (n=15) and 65.2% (n=15) of faculty were visiting faculty for the first and second cohorts respectively. Of 32 facilitators involved in curriculum delivery, 12 (37.5%) were physically present with the students for all or part of their teaching and training engagements. Up to 18.5% of facilitators were consistently present at UGHE throughout the inaugural surgery rotation. Only five of the faculty were engaged in clinical surgical service delivery at Butaro District Hospital in any way across both cohorts, and of these 1 was a local surgeon.

Clerkship Facilitators (Fellows, Faculty)

Figure 1: Distribution of Faculty (in-person and virtual)

There is only 1 attending surgeon at BDH, and no general practitioners assigned to surgery. Visiting faculty were on site at Butaro for a range of 1-4 weeks. Table 1 shows the distribution of on-site visiting faculty through both rotations.

Table 1: On-site Visiting Faculty

Week	Thematic Areas	Rotation 1 Visiting faculty/fellows	Rotation 2 Visiting faculty	BDH specialist
Week 1	Introduction to Surgery/Simulation Week*	Dr Callum Forbes	Dr Selam Degu Matt Hey Dr Gaston Dr Jean Paul	Dr Majyambere
Week 2	Perioperative Care/ Pediatrics*	Dr Callum Forbes	Dr Callum Forbes Dr Robin Petroze Rachel Koch	Dr Majyambere
Week 3	Abdomen	Dr Geoff Anderson Dr Callum Forbes	Dr Callum Forbes Rachel Koch	Dr Majyambere
Week 4	Gastrointestinal	Dr Geoff Anderson Dr Callum Forbes	Dr Callum Forbes Rachel Koch	Dr Majyambere
Week 5	Simulation Week/ Mid-Clerkship Evaluations	Dr Robert Riviello Dr Yihan Lin Dr Geoff Anderson Dr Callum Forbes Dr Selam Degu	Dr Callum Forbes Rachel Koch	Dr Majyambere
Week 6	Breast/Urology	Dr Robert Riviello Dr Innocent N Dr Callum Forbes Dr Selam Degu	Dr Callum Forbes Dr Rachel Koch Dr Innocent Nzeyimana Dr Dena	Dr Majyambere
Week 7	Plastic Surgery/Skin	Dr Callum Forbes Dr Selam Degu	Dr Callum Forbes Dr Dena	Dr Majyambere
Week 8	Orthopedics	Dr Megan Straghaun Dr Callum Forbes Dr Selam Degu	Dr Callum Forbes Dr Dena	Dr Majyambere
Week 9	Trauma/ Pediatrics	Prof Miliard Derbew Dr Megan Straghaun Dr Callum Forbes Dr Selam Degu	Dr Callum Forbes Dr Dena	Dr Majyambere
Week 10	Thoracic/ Neurosurgery	Dr Megan Straghaun Dr Callum Forbes Dr Selam Degu	Dr Callum Forbes Dr Dena	Dr Majyambere

4.1.1.2 Summary of Activities

The first 11 week University of Global Health Equity Junior Surgical clerkship started on Monday, 10th January, 2022 and ended on Friday, 25 March, 2022. The second cohort started on Monday, 28 March, 2022 and ended on Friday, 17 June, 2022. Students rotated on the surgical ward, operating room, the

recovery room, and the accident and emergency of BDH, and had in-class and simulation engagements on the UGHE Butaro Campus.

A total of 74 in-class and simulation sessions were facilitated within the 11 week rotations ranging from didactic in-person or virtual lectures, flipped classroom sessions, student and faculty-led seminars, simulation sessions, and tutorial sessions. The first week of the rotation was dedicated to simulation training for basics of surgery, while the final week was a summative evaluation week. See Appendix 2 for the schedule of topics covered.

The introductory surgical simulation week brought together UGHE simulation experts, Harvard PGSSC experts in simulation mentored by Brigham simulation specialists, GlobalSurg box proprietors from University of Colorado, and surgical educators to work on informed consent for surgery, aseptic technique, basic surgical skills including suturing techniques, resuscitation and basics of trauma care management. Up to 8 visiting educators participated in this impactful week that set the tone for the student’s immersion into clinical practice.

In clinical weeks, daily activities began by 7:30am with a morning report at the hospital and ended by 5:00pm following a 1 hour lecture. On Wednesdays students were fully on campus, while Friday engagements ended at 1:30pm. Each student had clinical call duty for 3 hours a night each week. Table 2 shows a detailed schedule of daily activities.

Table 2: Surgery 301 Student Daily Schedule

		MONDAY	TUESDAY	WEDNESDAY	THURSDAY	FRIDAY
Morning Clinical Sessions (7:30am-3:30pm)	7:30-8:30am	Morning Meetings	Morning Meetings	Lecture (8:15-9:45am) CBCL/Lectures (10:00-12:00pm) Office hours (1:00-3:30pm)	Morning Meetings	Morning Meetings
		Ward/OPD/OR/Anesthesia/Emergency	Ward/OPD/OR/Anesthesia/Emergency		Ward/OPD/OR/Anesthesia/Emergency	Ward/OPD/OR/Anesthesia/Emergency
		Ward/OPD/OR/Anesthesia/Emergency	Ward/OPD/OR/Anesthesia/Emergency		Lectures/CBCL/Flipped Class/Seminar (2-4pm)	Simulation (11:00-1:30pm)
Afternoon Lectures (4:00-5:00pm)		Lectures /Flipped Class/Seminar	Lectures /Flipped Class/Seminar	Lectures / Flipped Class/ Seminar	Lectures / Flipped Class/ Seminar	
Clinical Call Duty (7:00-10:00pm)		ON CALL	ON CALL	ON CALL	ON CALL	ON CALL

Clinical activities at BDH were organized in three 2-week rotations of 5 students each (with 1 week of repeat rotations) through the Surgical Ward/Operating Room, the Surgical Ward/Out-patient Department, the Emergency Room/Anesthesia (including plaster of paris application service and recovery room care). These postings were paired to maximize opportunities for learning, pre-empting the possible challenge of surgical volume.

4.1.1.3 Summary of Learning

Clinical instruction was largely given at Butaro District Hospital, while didactics were at the UGHE campus. Specific learning exposures occurred through the following:

Morning Report

- A daily clinical morning report held at BDH on Monday, Tuesday, Thursday and Friday which involved presentation of surgical cases encountered during the previous call duty. Three learners

had 20 minutes each to discuss a unique surgical case. These sessions were attended by all students, visiting fellows, in-country visiting faculty, the BDH surgeon, surgery intern, and occasionally a GP. This contributed to group learning, patient updates, and allowed for a holistic team approach to surgical care.

Clinical Work

- Following the morning report, learners went into their sub-rotations. Ward work was performed with the nurses on the surgical ward including wound care, surgical drain maintenance, vital signs, and bedside surgery like incision and drainage. New patients were clerked and worked up for surgery. These were followed by bedside teachings, with student presentations, bedside tutorials, and teaching rounds. During bedside teaching, students were assisted to develop clinical reasoning using metacognitive techniques and peer-to-peer learning methods. They also were taught physical examination skills, differential diagnosis, investigations, diagnoses, treatment options, and complications of care with emphasis on the peculiarities of a district or a referral hospital setting.

Structured learning in classroom sessions

- Ten thematic areas were covered within 10 weeks with a simulation intensive bootcamp held on week 5. Ratio of virtual to in person didactics was about 3:1. Didactics included traditional lectures and flipped classrooms, case-based clinical learning sessions, simulation-based learning for both procedures and scenarios, student-led seminars, and faculty-led seminars. The sessions enjoyed a mix of both local and international faculty. All sessions were covered appropriately, but the order of lectures was frequently adjusted to accommodate the visiting clinical facilitators' engagements (e.g emergency surgery, or extended stay in OR etc). This implied that the sequence of didactics was often disrupted, but all sessions were eventually covered.

Table 3 lists out the entrustable professional activities from expected competencies and faculty assessments on whether or not they were achieved.

Table 3: Achievement of Entrustable Professional Activities

Expectation for Junior Surgery Clerkship	Entrustable Professional Activity	Achieved/Borderline/Not-achieved
Execution with reactive supervision, i.e., on request and quickly available	Document a clinical encounter in the patient record	Borderline-theoretically achieved (limited permissions to documenting in patient records)
	Provide an oral presentation of a clinical encounter	Achieved
	Form clinical questions and retrieve evidence to advance patient care	Achieved
Execution with direct, proactive supervision	Gather a history and perform a physical exam adapted to the patient's clinical situation	Achieved
	Formulate and justify prioritized differential diagnosis following a clinical encounter.	Achieved
	Formulate an initial plan of investigation based on the diagnostic hypotheses	Achieved
	Recommend and interpret common diagnostic screening tests	Achieved

	Give or receive a patient handover to transition care responsibility (particularly refer a patient appropriately and adequately prepare the patient for transfer)	Borderline (limited permissions to documenting in patient records)
	Recognize a patient requiring urgent or emergency surgical care and initiate evaluation and management	Achieved
	Obtain informed consent for tests and/or procedures	Achieved
	Educate patients on surgical disease management, health promotion and preventive medicine	Achieved
	Perform general physician procedures relevant to surgery (NG tube, venipuncture, catheterization)	Achieved
	Evaluate and manage a patient with an inguinal hernia	Borderline- (Non-operative/theoretical component achieved, operative components deficient- poor case volume and case mix at BDH)* Only 6 herniorrhaphies were performed during student hours across both cohorts
	Evaluate and manage a patient with right lower quadrant pain	Borderline- (Non-operative component achieved, operative component deficient-poor case volume and case mix at BDH) * No appendicectomies were performed during student hours across both cohort
	Evaluation and initial management of a patient presenting with trauma	Achieved (simulation enhanced)
	Perform other consensus minor to intermediate clinical surgical procedures (See Delphi result list e.g. excision of lumps, bumps, debridement, drain removal))	Borderline (poor case volume and case mix at BDH)
	Recognize and initiate referral and transfer of surgical patients beyond the capacity of the district hospital's scope of care	Achieved
Observation but no execution by the trainee, even with direct supervision	Formulate, communicate, and implement surgical management plans	Achieved
	Collaborate as member of an interprofessional team	Achieved
	Identify system failures and contribute to a culture of safety and improvement (participate in surgical health quality improvement initiatives e.g., surgical checklist)	Achieved
	[Observe] other consensus major clinical surgical procedures (See Delphi result list)	Not achieved (poor case volume and case mix at BDH) *35.7% of all general surgery cases were breast surgeries

4.1.1.4 Student evaluations

A combination of formative (40%) and summative (60%) assessments were used to evaluate learners during this clerkship.

Formative assessments consisted of the following-

1. *Mini-Consultation Evaluation Exercise (Mini-CEX)*: This was performed on week 5 of the rotation with rich, individualized verbal and written feedback, followed by a signed student compact for improvement but did not contribute to the final grade.

2. *Faculty evaluations (10%)*: This was joint preceptor feedback on students' performance in rounds, bedside, lectures, case presentations, attendance, and other aspects of the rotation.
3. *Logbook reviews (10%)*: Documentation of observed, assisted and performed surgical cases, clinical encounters and reflections was graded based on the faculty's expectations and available cases.
4. *Clinical case reports (10%)*: Trainers assessed write-ups on cases submitted every 2 weeks which included a diagnostic and therapeutic plan with detailed history, examination, investigations, problem list, differential diagnoses, treatment and complications
5. *Assignments (10%)*: These were graded in-class assignments or requested group submissions.

Summative assessments (on weeks 5 and 11) included the following-

1. *Mid-attachment Objective Structured Clinical Examination (OSCE) (20%)*
2. *End Module Multiple Choice Questions (20%)*
3. *Summative OSCE (20%)*

4.1.1.5 Student performance

For both cohorts, students performed satisfactorily (with scores ranging from 66.68- 86.99%). Final grades included 6 As, 15 B+s, 8 Bs, and only 1 C+. Figure 2 shows student performance across both cohorts. There was no statistically significant difference in the average scores between the cohorts (cohort 1- 82%; cohort 2- 79%).

Figure 2: Student performance across cohorts

4.1.1.6 Clerkship site

BDH is a 150-bed public hospital located in Burera district of northern Rwanda opened in 2011. In addition to the four main clinical wards (surgery, obstetrics and gynecology, pediatrics, and internal medicine), BDH hosts a cancer center of excellence that provides high quality cancer

treatment to patients from Rwandan and the neighboring countries. Nearly, 350,000 patients are served by this Partners In Health-supported hospital.

4.2 Retrospective curriculum review

Student survey responses

Students were asked to provide their opinion on a range of aspects of the curriculum delivery through completion of a paper based survey as per Appendix 3. Survey response rate was 100%.

Asked to provide an overall rating of the quality of the junior surgical clerkship 66.7% (20/30) rated the program as either 'excellent' or 'very good' (figure 3). This aligned with the fact that the majority of students felt that UGHE faculty were very supportive with 90% recommending that they should continue to lead delivery of the clerkship for subsequent interactions (figure 4).

Figure 3 - overall clerkship student rating

Figure 4 - should current faculty continue on surgical clerkship - student opinion

Figure 5 - should clerkship be continued at BDH - student opinion

In contrast, less than 50% of students (13/30) agreed that the curriculum should continue to be delivered at BDH (figure 5).

Looking in more detail at the feelings of the students regarding the teaching environment at BDH, we assessed the students' opinions of both the volume and variety of cases across all clinical areas (OR, surgical ward, ER, and OPD clinic). The opinion regarding the adequacy of volume varied across areas with the highest proportion of students feeling that the volume was 'excellent' or 'good' in clinic (26/30, 86.7%), whereas the lowest proportion of students felt volume was 'excellent' or 'good' in the OR (8/30, 26.7%) (figures 6-9).

Figure 6 - OR volume was sufficient

Figure 7 - ward volume was sufficient

Figure 8 - clinic volume was sufficient

Figure 9 - ED volume was sufficient

This pattern was mirrored when exploring students opinions relating to case variety with only 33.3% of students (10/30) rating the case variety as either 'excellent' or 'good' whereas 86.7% of students (26/30) felt clinic case variety was either 'excellent' or 'good' (figures 10-13).

Figure 10 - OR patient variety was sufficient

Figure 11 - ward patient variety was sufficient

Figure 12 - clinic patient variety was sufficient

Figure 13 - ED patient variety was sufficient

Of the four clinical areas, students felt the surgical ward was the area where they were most able to contribute positively to patient care. In the surgical ward 80% of students (24/30) felt they were able to contribute to patient care and 76.7% (23/30) felt the ward provided 'good' or 'excellent' opportunities to present cases and perform care (figures 14-15). This contrasted with the OR where only 56.7% of students (17/30) felt they were able to contribute positively to patient care and just 20% (6/30) were of the opinion that the OR provided 'good' or 'excellent' opportunities to perform or assist in surgeries (figures 16-17).

Figure 14 - I felt able to contribute to patient care on the ward

Figure 15 - ward opportunities to present and perform care

Figure 16 - I felt able to contribute to patient care in OR

Figure 17 - OR opportunities to perform or assist in surgeries

4.3 Staff survey

Using a paper-based questionnaire, BDH clinical staff were surveyed on a range of aspects of curriculum delivery following completion of both cohorts of the clerkship (Appendix 4).

In total we received 19 responses from clinicians in a variety of roles including surgeons, medical officers and interns, ward nurses, OR nurses, emergency department nurses, and non-physician anaesthetists (figure 18). Irrespective of their role, the staff overwhelmingly agreed that they would welcome medical students back to BDH for future surgical clerkships (figure 19) and the majority (94.7%, 18/19) rated the junior surgical clerkship as either ‘excellent’, ‘very good’, or ‘good’ (figure 20).

Figure 18 - role

Figure 19 - I would welcome students back

Figure 20 - overall BDH staff rating of surgical clerkship

Staff felt generally well equipped to teach the students with 73.7% (14/19) and 84.2% (16/19) agreeing that they felt qualified to teach medical students and felt they had enough time to devote to teaching respectively (figures 21-22). In line with the opinion of students, the majority of staff members (63.2%, 12/19) agreed that the students contributed positively to patient care in the hospital during their surgical clerkship (figure 23).

Figure 21 - I felt qualified to teach

Figure 22 - I had enough time to teach

Figure 23 - students contributed positively to patient care

In relation to the UGHE faculty, the relationship seemed generally positive with most (94.7%, 18/19) 'strongly agreeing' that the faculty were helpful with teaching and 68.4% (13/19) agreeing that the communication from UGHE faculty was clear. Of note however, there were also a significant minority (26.3%, 5/19) that felt there was scope for improvement with regards to communication from UGHE faculty (Figure 24-25).

Figure 24 - UGHE faculty were helpful with teaching

Figure 25 - UGHE faculty communication was clear

In contrast to the predominant opinion of the student body, staff unanimously believed that patient volume (100%) and variety (94.7%, 18/19) at BDH was sufficient for the students' learning needs (figure 26-27). Where the staff did feel there could be improvement related to the teaching environment at BDH was with regards to workforce capacity. This was evidenced by the fact that 42.1% (8/19) of the staff surveyed disagreed to some extent that workforce capacity was sufficient for teaching and training (figure 28).

Figure 26 - patient volume at BDH is sufficient for teaching and training medical students

Figure 27 - patient case mix at BDH is sufficient for teaching and training medical students

Figure 28 - workforce capacity at BDH sufficient for teaching and training medical students

4.4 Focus groups and qualitative survey responses

There were some emerging trends and themes from both the student survey and the staff survey. As a means of exploring these further we conducted focus groups with the medical students following completion of their clerkship. All 30 students attended these focus groups which were conducted over a 60 minute period in groups of 6 with students from both cohorts mixed within the focus groups. These sessions were recorded and then transcribed verbatim. Following on from this the transcript were coded with codes subsequently collated into categories.

In reviewing both the qualitative survey answers from students and BDH staff, and the focus group codes and categories four main themes emerged. We titled these themes as ‘Teaching and Learning’, ‘Patient Care’, ‘Clinical Learning Experience’, and ‘Working Support and Relationships’. Below, we summarize our findings relevant to each of these four themes with table 4 outlining the ‘enhancers’ and ‘barriers’ to success related to each of these four themes.

4.4.1 Teaching and Learning

Whilst students rated their experience with faculty positively (as evidenced in the above survey responses), there were also high levels of agreement that they did not have enough faculty supervision during their surgical rotations primarily due to the ratio of faculty to student numbers.

One of the student focus group participants observed:

“We had only one faculty [member] and he was in the operating room almost every day. So if you were not in the operating room, there wasn't really any other faculty most of the time in the wards or in the emergency department who was teaching us and so most of the time we felt like we were on our own” (focus group participant-1).

Another commented:

“I feel like I contributed to the patient care, but I was able to do so because I had some supervision. Doctor D [UGHE faculty member] was very helpful, she could encourage us to actively participate in care of the patient, but if we did not have her at the ward, I think we could not have been able to do so”

BDH staff agreed with the students that there should be greater faculty supervision of students during their clinical rotation, primarily realized as greater numbers of faculty members present in the different clinical areas. One BDH staff member commented:

“There is a need for more faculty that work closely with students at the hospital”

Another stated:

“I suggest that the UGHE faculty accompanying the student work closely with the medical doctor in the ward round.”

The above barriers were coupled with the fact that BDH staff often felt too short staffed to devote their time to teaching and training the students and did not feel comfortable with the aims and objectives of the student rotation. One of the non-physician anesthetists commented:

"We don't maximize our time with students because the department of surgery is short staffed. We are only 6 while we were supposed to be 11. This is a big challenge for us."

Another noted:

"We need more physician anesthesiologist"

A nurse also observed:

"The nursing staff is short staffed. We would be happy if we were given some motivation because it is time consuming to teach the students."

Another nurse commented:

"I wish that UGHE faculty would explain to me what they expect from me at the beginning of the rotation."

One BDH staff member observed:

"We didn't know the level of knowledge of the students and the objective of the rotation. Hence we had troubles knowing how to help them"

This was corroborated by observations from the student body.

"They [BDH staff] didn't know the level of our knowledge or the gaps that we had."

Despite this, students expressed that some BDH staff were eager to teach them.

"I remember that one day in the oncology clinic, the specialist gave us two individual rooms to take a medical history and do a physical examination. Later, we presented to him our findings and dedicated some time to give us feedback. I can say that I learnt a lot that day."

These views were consistent with those provided by BDH. One staff member observed:

"The students were very active. We enjoyed having them around."

4.4.2 Patient care

Accommodating medical students for the first time, understandably required adaptation to existing patient care models and structures at BDH. We aimed to assess the impact that hosting medical students might have on the quality of patient care.

As highlighted in both the student and BDH staff survey results, the presence of students in the clinical areas led to a perceived improvement in patient care.

One student commented:

"I felt like patients who had UGHE students were benefiting more because we took time to discuss with patients about their diagnosis and educate them about lifestyle modifications they did not much about."

In contrast however, some staff observed the potential downsides to having students in the clinical areas with one anesthetist observing:

"Having students in the OR extends the operations."

We also more broadly assessed student and staff perspectives regarding the care delivered at BDH. Low numbers of specialists and resource limitations were highlighted by students as the main barriers to patient care at BDH. The students were mindful that BDH is a district level hospital, however they felt that much can still be done even at the district hospital level. They observed that numerous surgeries had been postponed during the two clerkship cohorts because the hospital had run out of materials such as endotracheal tubes, anesthesia medications, and sterile scrub gowns. Students also believed that their learning was hindered by bottlenecks in patient care caused by delays in requesting, processing, and reporting of laboratory investigations. Some students narrations regarding this are as follow:

“The OR could spend one or two weeks without anesthesia medications. For someone who was rotating in the OR during that period, it is clear that he/she will have a limited operative exposure.” (focus group participant-3)

“Imagine requesting for an FBC and it takes about 3 or 4 days from Monday till Thursday or requesting a peripheral blood smear and after a week, you find the request form in the patient file and no one has taken time to take the sample to the laboratory. That is not good for patient care.” (focus group participant -4).

Although workforce shortage was highlighted as a potential barrier to patient care by the students in both cohorts, they also felt that it gave them more room to engage in patient care. When asked if they felt as they were contributing to patient care, students responded as follow:

“I could also find some postoperative complications such as Atelectasis, pneumonias and report them to Doctor M [BDH general surgeon] as he was always busy, so I think personally we were helpful.” (focus group participant).

“We took like big time with patients, talking to them about those lifestyle modifications they didn't know much more about it.” (focus group participant).

“...yeah, because we were also helping the nurses with some procedures such wound dressing, and IV line insertion.”(focus group participant).

Students also believed that undertaking multidisciplinary ward rounds with physician specialists, general practitioners and nurses all present, would have improved patient care as well as simultaneously boosting their learning experience. One student reported:

“We needed everyone say the GP, the nurse, the external faculty and the specialist not for supervision but to teach us, and then gain some of practical skills in order to apply them to a patient.”

Some students observed that in contrast, when ward rounds were conducted separately, patients often had different therapeutic plans made by general practitioners and physician specialists which potentially affected quality of care. One student explained:

“In the ward round, you could find that the GP's treatment plan is different from what the specialists is saying or sometimes the specialist had to change the treatment plan and stamp in the patient file. I guess if things were done in a team, we could learn better and patient care would improve.”

Students also highlighted some aspects of the care delivered at BDH that they though contributed to positive patient outcomes. Having high quality in-hospital nutrition, and the high standards of hygiene positively improved patient outcome, as explained by one student:

“...but when it comes to things like provision of food, the hygiene, and some other kinds of social support; I haven't gone to other hospitals, but I think this makes the standards of care better compared to other hospitals.”

Another student added:

“...when compared to other hospitals, it (patient care) is really good right here because of the support from Partners In Health.”

4.4.3 Clinical exposure

As highlighted in the survey responses, a significant minority of students felt that the volume and variety of patients, particularly in the OR, was insufficient for their learning. When discussed in more detail, students confirmed that the low volume and variety of surgical cases was the main barrier to their learning experience. Below are quotes from students:

“I think that it hindered our learning capacity. Because for example in the surgical ward, we had a few cases of fractures and ulcers, and the majority were breast cancer patients. Hence, we did not get a chance to learn how to exam other patients with non-cancer conditions or at least do pre or postoperative care.”

“Cases were mainly breast cancers and any other interesting patients were automatically referred to Kigali or to Musanze because of the low capacity of the OR.”

Students felt that the issue of low volume and variety of cases is caused in part by the fact that BDH is a cancer center of excellence. Students observed that this meant a majority of the patients had cancer-related conditions and were given priority over non-malignant conditions, including many of the common surgical conditions you might see in other district-level hospitals. Benign conditions were treated as elective cases or in some cases referred to other hospitals in Kigali or in Musanze. One student was quoted as saying:

“I could see some patients presenting in the OPD, but then they were always given a rendez-vous. So it was also a challenge. Most of the surgeries were for cancer related things such as mastectomies and Abdominoperineal Resections (APR) for intestinal tumors. Things like that, but no general conditions surgeries.”

Some students felt that having just one specialist surgeon and one OR contributed to too few surgeries being performed at BDH. They also noted that the low capacity of the OR meant that procedures other than Caesarean sections were often unable to be performed.

“Even if BDH had many cases, as we have observed, it doesn't have enough surgeons as well as enough ORs. Sometimes we had visiting surgeons but since we had one OR, still a few procedures were performed. So, the insufficiency of OR as well as having one surgeon limited the number of cases we could have observed during our clerkship.”

Unlike the students, the vast majority of the staff at BDH felt that volume and variety of cases were sufficient enough to train medical students. As discussed above, they felt that the main barrier to implementing a successful clinical rotation at BDH was the relatively low number of clinical staff. One staff member noted:

“There are enough surgical patients for students to learn from. However, it would be good to increase the number of specialities at BDH”

4.4.4 Working support and clerkship organization

The relationship between the students and BDH staff was also evaluated through the focus groups and in the qualitative survey questions. Students found that the majority of staff were very supportive and happy to teach them.

This was reciprocated in the observations from staff who felt the students' attitudes were excellent and that students were motivated to learn and engage with patient care. One staff member commented:

“The students are very disciplined. It would be good to give them more time at the hospital”

Another noted:

“We would be happy to have them more often”

However some students did note that a small number of the staff were less cooperative. This was particularly highlighted when students made a suggestion or were asked something they do not know.

A student reported: *“...if you forget something or if you don't know how to do some procedures, they could react in a harsh way.*

Additionally they often felt these suggestions were not welcomed by the staff. A student reported:

...people tell you that this not how things are done here, just cooled down.

A number of students felt that the staff at BDH were initially reluctant to teach them but noticed that this attitude improved as time went by.

“When we started, some BDH staff didn't know what we really wanted. But with time, you could see that they started to get involved in teaching us.”

“I guess because they saw that we knew how to take a medical history and do a good physical exam; and we really wanted to be engaged in patient care, they started to push us and make us responsible for our patient. But that came later in our clerkship.”

Regarding the organization of the clerkship, students often felt there was a time conflict between clinic experience and exposure and the didactic teaching (lectures, flipped classrooms, student-led seminars etc). As a result many expressed the wish that all classes be recorded so that students who opt to spend time in the OR do not have to miss lectures but instead can review them back retrospectively. One student wished:

“If they (students in the OR) could be excused, but still the lectures are recorded for them to catch up later, that would be great. Because leaving the OR in the middle of an operation does not give the full exposure of the surgical care.”

Furthermore, some students pointed out that often afternoons spent at the hospital were not very productive as there was nothing planned and much of the clinical work had been completed in the morning. Students suggested scheduling clinical teaching in the afternoon (eg bedside teaching) would allow them to maximize their clinical exposure in the mornings (for example, by attending working wards rounds etc) whilst also benefiting from more productive afternoons spent at the hospital.

“We didn't have much things to do in the afternoon.”

“To maximize our time at the hospital and avoid some people feeling useless in the afternoon, ...I was thinking maybe in the afternoon we can have a bedside teaching.”

Similarly, the students wanted the ability to be able to undertake self-directed or book-based learning during times when there were minimal clinical activities happening in the hospital. At present there is not a space devoted to students to undertake such work at the hospital and thus many expressed the wish to be allowed to return to campus to do some reading on their own. Below is a quote from a student:

“And for students who are not in the OR, they could come back to the campus because in the afternoon, it feels so weird to see 5 medical students just sitting and reading from their books instead of rounding on the patient.”

BDH staff also felt that the rotation would have been better if they had known what is expected from them.

Table 4: Themes, barriers, and enhancers

Themes	Barriers	Enhancers
Teaching and learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Limited faculty supervision - The objectives were not clear to students and BDH staff - BDH staff did not know the level of knowledge of the students - The staff have a high workload - Too many students in the OR and the ward. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Visiting faculty were very resourceful - Dr M [BDH specialist surgeon] is a good educator and is motivated to teach. - BDH staff are eager to teach - There is a good relationship between the UGHE staff and BDH staff - The students have a professional relationship with

		<p>BDH staff</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Shortage of staff gives students room for more involvement.
Patient care	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - BDH is short staffed - In particular there are few physician specialists at BDH - Wards are not multidisciplinary - The hospital often encounters supply chain issues - BDH as a district hospital isn't set up to effectively assess and manage patients with trauma - Few laboratory investigations are done at BDH or if performed are often reported late - Accommodating students potentially places further strain on the system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Because of workforce shortages there is greater scope for students to be engaged in patient care - Support provided by PIH - The patients are given food - BDH has good hygiene practices - BDH is working toward becoming a teaching hospital
Clinical exposure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Low volume and variety of surgical cases - Surgeries were canceled or delayed due to resources limitations and supply chain issues - Difficulties in following up a patient throughout their hospital stay due to students having to rotate through different clinical areas - Interesting cases are often referred to other referral hospitals - There is only one surgeon and two ORs (with one reserved for OBGYN cases) - Some examples of poor teamwork between BDH staff - Hospital scrub availability was limited, affecting students ability to assist or observe surgeries 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The students were motivated to learn - The hospital is expanding, so there is more room for teaching - Good volume of minor procedures
Working support and clerkship organization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Some BDH staff reacted badly when approached by students - Students' interventions were sometimes not considered during ward rounds - Initially, some staff were reluctant to teach the students - Students missed some lectures while they were in the OR - There was no formalized clinical teaching program in the afternoon - Lack of on-site study space for students 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Most staff are very supportive - Most faculty members were eager to teach and answer students' questions - There are young GPs at BDH who are very eager to teach the students

4.5 Workforce review

The theater complex at Butaro District Hospital comprises 2 adjoined operating rooms with an adjacent post-anaesthesia care area. This complex is staffed by a combination of the following workforce: one specialist physician surgeon, 2 specialist physician obstetrician gynecologists, 5 non-physician anesthesia providers and 7 theater nurses. In addition there are 8 surgical ward nurses working in the surgical ward and a total of 10 ancillary staff across both the operating rooms and the surgical ward.. Through a shift-based rostering system the theater complex generally functions in-hours (8-4pm) with 2 non-physician anesthesia providers and 2 theater nurses, and out-of-hours with 1 non-physician anesthesia provider and 1 theater nurse. Specialist physician providers for both surgery, and obstetrics and gynecology are on-site during in-hours and available for consultation and in-person attendance as required out-of-hours. Whilst Cesarean sections are generally completed independently by General Practitioners attached to the maternity unit, the specialist physician providers are otherwise present and 'scrubbed-in' for all theater cases.

4.6 Surgical Caseload

A comprehensive paper-based logbook of completed theater cases is kept contemporaneously updated by the on-shift theater staff at BDH. Logbook data was retrospectively reviewed for the dates corresponding to the 2 cohorts of the MBBS class of 2025 junior surgical clerkship conducted at BDH (10/1/22 - 17/6/22 inclusive) and collated as follows.

A total of 607 theater cases were logged of which 286 (47.12%) were undertaken during cohort 1 and 321 were undertaken during cohort 2. Of these cases, 462 (76.1%) were obstetrics and gynecology cases with 431 (71.0%) being Cesarean sections (figure 29).

Figure 29 - overall count per category

There were a total of 144 'surgical' cases undertaken during the 2 cohorts of which 115 were commenced 'in-hours' (constituting any case that started from 0800-2200hrs on a Monday through Friday inclusive and not during the students simulation and examination weeks, nor during national holidays) and 29 of which were commenced 'out-of-hours'.

Of the in-hours cases, 56 (48.7%) occurred during cohort 1 and 59 occurred during cohort 2 with an average number of cases per week of 6.39 and a median of 7 (range 1-10). Figure 30 shows the number of in-hours surgical cases per week over the course of the two cohorts. Given that each student was allocated to the operating room for 3 weeks of their 9 weeks of in-hours rotation time this equated to an estimated average number of surgical procedures per student of 19.17.

In terms of case mix, the most common category of procedure was 'breast' (n=41, 35.7%), of which 33 were Modified Radical Mastectomies, followed by 'soft tissue biopsy' (n=21, 18.3%), and 'soft tissue

infection' (n=11, 9.6%). Of note 10 (8.7%) laparotomies, 7 (6.1%) herniorrhaphies, and 6 (5.2%) skin grafts were performed (Figure 31).

Day to day distribution of theater caseload varied widely with the majority of cases being undertaken on Tuesdays (n=35, 30.4%), Wednesdays (n=40, 34.8%), and Thursdays (n=35, 30.4%). Only 2 (1.7%) and 3 (2.6%) cases were undertaken on Monday and Friday respectively (Figure 32).

Figure 30 - in-hours surgery count per week

Figure 31 - in-hours surgery count per category

Figure 32 - in-hours surgery count per day

4.7 Student exposure

Student logbooks were reviewed and compared to the above theater logs. In utilizing their logbooks, students were able to log cases as 'observed', 'assisted', or 'performed'. In addition students were also encouraged to log non-procedural clinical interactions for example when clerking or taking a history from/examining a surgical patient. Of note, many of the procedures logged by students encompassed more than merely theater procedures but also included minor procedures conducted in the emergency room as well as ward procedures such as wound dressings, bladder catheterisation, and peripheral intravenous catheter insertion.

Students observed a mean and median of 23.5 and 18 (range 3 - 71) procedures respectively according to their logbooks (Figure 33). With a significant difference in procedures observed between the two cohorts (mean C1 = 33.6, mean C2 = 13.3, $p = 0.0005$).

Students assisted in a mean and median of 6.00 and 4 (range 0-19) procedures respectively, with no significant difference between cohorts (Figure 34). Concerning procedures performed, students logged a mean of 16.34 procedures (median 5, range 4-42) with again, no significant difference between cohorts (Figure 35).

With regards to cases logged, students logged a mean and median of 42.33 and 41 cases respectively (Figure 36) which correlated to a mean and median total number of clinical encounters (cases plus procedures observed, assisted, and performed) of 88.13 and 86 respectively (Figures 37-38). There was no significant difference in cohorts with respect to the total number of clinical encounters.

Figure 33 - number of procedures observed

Figure 34 - number of procedures assisted

Figure 35 - number of procedures performed

Figure 36 - number of clinical cases

Figure 37 - total number of encounters

Figure 38 - histogram of total clinical encounters

4.8 Delays and cancellations

During the final 2 months (21/4/22 - 17/4/22 inclusive) of the junior surgical clerkship an additional logbook of delayed or canceled cases was kept in light of increasing postponements and cancellations anecdotally. Figure 25 shows a mind map fishbone diagram describing surgery cancellations and delays that affected learning in the operating room.

Figure 39: Fishbone diagram showing causes of surgery delays and cancellations

4.9 Further Faculty Observations

Faculty and fellows actively engaged in curriculum delivery also noted delays in licensing of visiting faculty. This often delayed clinical and teaching engagement. Professionalism of the students was also identified by faculty as a challenge, particularly in the area of timeliness.

5.0 DISCUSSION

This review uncovers a number of salient learning points that can help to enhance and improve the clinical clerkship experience for learners, trainers, and clinicians.

From the perspective of both medical students and BDH clinical staff, one of the greatest strengths of the clerkship was the positive relationships between students, BDH faculty, and UGHE faculty resulting from the program. These relationships created a positive learning environment, in which stakeholders were invested in both patient care and the students' learning experience. Hospital staff noted the need for formal introduction of visiting faculty to all cadres of hospital surgical care providers with a clear delineation of their roles as a way to further improve relationship building between BDH and UGHE staff. Improvement in communication between visiting UGHE surgical educators and BDH staff was also noted as a place for improvement. The extent to which the language barrier between non-Kinyarwanda speaking faculty/international volunteers and local care providers might have contributed to this perception was not determined. Recruiting Kinyarwanda speaking visiting faculty from within Rwanda can help mitigate this. To further enhance the positive learning environment, an introductory session between all BDH surgical staff and core UGHE surgical educators would be beneficial prior to commencement of the next cohort. A formal introductory meeting with surgical staff for every visiting faculty as a distinct event might be challenging, however, existing surgical team meetings should be leveraged to introduce visiting educators and fellows in an ongoing manner.

Learners expressed their perception that some staff seemed reluctant to engage in teaching activities (particularly earlier in the posting). This dynamic needs to be explored further through staff focus group interviews. However, one theme that emerged from the staff surveys that can explain this dynamic was the fact that almost unanimously, BDH clinical staff felt there was a need to financially and otherwise 'motivate' or reimburse BDH staff engaged in teaching. The need for financial motivation to engage in student education was pervasive. Certain staff members even alluded to being 'promised' some form of reimbursement. UGHE faculty, however, are not aware of any promised reimbursements for involvement in student training. This suggests that there needs to be more open avenues of communication between the BDH staff and UGHE prior to future iterations of the clerkship to clarify misconceptions of promised financial benefits. Ongoing avenues for UGHE/BDH surgical staff to network and openly communicate can help to address such miscommunication. Information sessions provided by UGHE for BDH staff would help ensure there are no perceptions of unfulfilled promises on reimbursement packages. In addition, UGHE should consider bringing tangible benefits to BDH staff, including staff training, avenues for Continuous Medical Education with credits (for instance adding credits to morning reports), and involving junior staff and nurses as research assistants on in-hospital UGHE related studies from which they can earn stipends.

Both students and BDH clinicians emphasized the need for clearer communication of expectations prior to commencement of the program. BDH staff expected clearer communication on what they should expect from the students in terms of their level of knowledge and ability, on what was expected of them by UGHE, and on how (and to what extent) they should be driving the students' learning in the clinical environment. To a certain extent, these shortfalls might be expected for a new clerkship in its first year of implementation^{11,12}. In established undergraduate programs, staff have had long-term experience in staff-student interactions, and have learned what to expect from medical students. Formal attempts to set expectations occurred prior to the start of the posting. Firstly, BDH faculty underwent a 3-day pre-clerkship training organized by UGHE and Harvard. However, this training was not targeted at more junior doctors, General Practitioners, nurses and anesthesiologists. A surgery-specific introductory session for all cadres of BDH clinical staff with translation into Kinyarwanda, and clerkship pamphlets describing

expected competencies and entrustable professional activities may be beneficial in clarifying this for BDH staff.

Perhaps, the student's expectations of the posting were higher than those of faculty in some respects. Other studies show that this is not unusual¹³. Despite the stated competencies and Entrustable Professional Activities, they expected to be heavily involved in operating room and clinical work at a more expert level in their first rotation. There was the pervasive notion that they were not contributing enough to patient care.

Students suggested that expectations of how they should spend their working day in the hospital (outside of direct faculty interactions such as the morning report, or bedside teachings) were unclear. Similar findings have been documented in literature¹². All learners participated in a mandatory pre-clerkship introductory session facilitated by the course coordinators, and had access to the syllabus, posting details, and specific advice on the posting. In addition, a combined morning report between Internal Medicine and Surgery focused on self-directed learning and the difference between pre-clinical learning and clinical education was held midway into the second student rotation. Furthermore, there were 20 hours per clerkship dedicated to office hours which potentially created an interface for clarification of expectations and discussion of individual challenges. However, less than 10% of this time was filled. Despite these attempts at setting expectations, and providing guidance, as a new program, it is important to be cognisant of this perception from the student body. In well established surgical education programs, there is a process of 'generational' information sharing and generic cross pollination across cohorts. More senior students continuously and organically share their experiences with students from more junior years¹⁴. This dynamic was absent in this pioneering year, but will gradually build up as cohorts that have experienced surgery rotations increase. In addition, the multiplier effect of a residency program is missing from the district hospital context. With a residency in place, consultant surgeons iteratively share expectations with senior residents, senior residents ensure that expectations for junior residents and interns are clarified in a continuous manner, and junior residents express expectations for interns and medical students in an ongoing fashion¹⁵⁻¹⁷. This dynamic may be lost as a single attending surgeon, or sparse faculty can not always be with the students in all rotation locations.

Another aspect of curriculum delivery that both students and BDH clinical staff emphasized was their desire for students to be more closely supervised by UGHE faculty members. This was emphasized despite the fact that students had daily morning reports moderated by UGHE faculty and fellows, and almost daily bedside teaching sessions, ward rounds or patient reviews. Students stated that, given they were in more junior stages of training, their learning was more effective when they had in-person faculty and fellows available to support them; either in a dedicated manner or in parallel to providing clinical care. Established surgery training programs in teaching hospitals rely heavily on peer-to-peer education, as additional medical student teaching is provided by residents, interns, and senior students integrated into a clinical team¹⁸. This lack of a clinical training network understandably heightened the felt need for closer faculty supervision. Students essentially requested an apprenticeship model that has been described in literature^{19,20}. As no specialist training programs are being established at BDH as of now, the employment of dedicated UGHE faculty or medical officers to facilitate student learning in the clinical setting and to share teaching workload with the limited number of clinical staff at BDH should be considered. The feasibility of having a dedicated UGHE surgeon at the emergency department, the wards and the operating room dedicated to teaching should be considered- however this raises the question of the availability of BDH clinician educators, as this responsibility should be shared. Survey responses showed that BDH staff felt that with closer UGHE faculty supervision provided to students, they, as clinicians, could focus entirely on patient care. In the absence of a surgical specialist training program at BDH,

coupled with a high patient to provider ratio (which often results in GPs and interns being overwhelmed by clinical care), emphasis must be placed on the necessity and benefits of integrating teaching into patient care for BDH providers.

The students frequently cited that they desired greater input from faculty and that learning was not maximized when they were present in clinical areas without direct UGHE faculty supervision. Whilst this is something to be aware of particularly in light of the fact that there is not a network of more senior students and trainees present at BDH, this may also reflect a need for improvement in independent, self-directed learning skills. UGHE faculty felt there was a heightened need for close supervision beyond what might be expected for the students' stage of training, and learners were not comfortable with deciding how to effectively utilize their time outside of faculty-led teaching.

Teaching hospitals appropriately integrate medical education into patient care. It should not be seen as striking a balance between patient care and medical education, as both are not mutually exclusive. For some health providers, this seems like a zero sum game. In implementing this new clinical clerkship at a new district hospital site, leadership must monitor appropriate integration of education into clinical care. With respect to the junior surgical clerkship at BDH, both students and BDH medical staff alike, felt that overall patient care benefited from the presence of medical students in the various clinical settings. Despite this, however, students expressed that they were constantly aware of the time conflict placed upon clinical staff in asking them to teach and train them, whilst also providing clinical care for patients. This was exacerbated by an impression that BDH faces significant workforce shortages, particularly with respect to surgical care, and staff are overworked. This perception was strongest concerning physician specialists such as surgeons and anaesthesiologists. This was also reflected in responses from surveyed BDH staff who expressed the need for additional specialist physicians to help transition BDH to a teaching hospital. Other programs have creatively addressed this by using video modules focused on "teaching when time is limited" or employing focused teaching methods useful for time constrained clinical settings like the "one-minute preceptor" model²¹⁻²³.

During implementation of the clerkship there were significant barriers to learning and training related to surgical volume and case mix. Low surgical volume and a limited spread of cases was often cited by students as the primary barrier to learning. On the contrary, BDH clinical staff felt that surgical volume and case mix was adequate. On review of the operating room logbook, it was evident that there was a heavy skew toward breast surgery at BDH. This resulted from the fact that BDH serves as a Regional Cancer Center of Excellence. One primary objective of the UGHE surgical curriculum delivered at BDH is to ensure that graduating students are well equipped for essential surgical care in the rural settings. An appropriate indicator of success would be that graduating students are able to assist and perform all of the three Bellwether procedures identified in the 2015 Lancet Commission of Global Surgery (cesarean section, laparotomy, management of open fractures)^{1(p20),24}. Of these 3, abdominal surgery and fracture management are key areas of focus within the new surgical curriculum. No orthopedics operations were performed at BDH within the period of the posting, and emergency laparotomies occurred approximately once every two weeks within the clerkship period. In the light of the focus of the UGHE curriculum, this exposure is clearly inadequate.

Deliberate improvements of the surgical case-mix is key for an effective surgical posting. Expansion of surgical interventions to gastro-intestinal surgeries for instance would help amplify exposure of students to laparotomies. Employment of an orthopedic specialist with focus on bone tumors and pathologic fractures would enrich the orthopedic surgery experience of BDH learners. The burden of trauma is also relatively low at BDH. One reason for this is the distance of the hospital from major roads and highways. The terrain does not make the facility the destination of first choice for trauma victims. BDH can

however leverage its designation as a center for excellence in cancer care by expanding the portfolio of cancer surgeries. This will have both patient-centered and learner-focused benefits. Simulation is a veritable tool that can be explored to fill these gaps in operative exposure²⁵. Virtual surgical exposures through telesurgery platforms like Allm and Proximie are innovative interventions that can expose learners to surgeries not held at BDH. Exploring the possibility of multi-site surgical postics to allow for a variety of cases and a more robust experience is a consideration²⁰.

Shortfalls in surgical equipment and stock out of medications were frequently highlighted as the cause of a significant number of surgical case cancellations and low surgical volume. From weeks 6 to 11 of the second cohort's clerkship, these logistic challenges led to the diversion of patients with surgical diagnoses to other hospitals, and the cancellation of all elective procedures in an attempt to reserve resources for urgent and emergent cases only. This was extremely disappointing to surgical clerkship students who, like other medical graduates globally, value scrubbing in as a useful part of their rotation²⁶. Other studies have similarly identified lack of suitable cases, constraints of time, and failure to provide medical students with opportunities as the most common barriers to learning²⁷.

From root cause analysis of delays and cancellations, the team identified that procurement issues (beyond the control of BDH and UGHE staff) were largely responsible. These supply chain breakdowns primarily occurred beyond district hospital level. However, factors were identified that could help mitigate delays and cancellations. Both BDH staff and students noted the challenge of insufficient scrubs and suggested the production of student-specific scrubs to ensure that clinical staff had adequate scrubs available. Similarly, clinical staff suggested UGHE supplying students with gloves and other single-use personal protective equipment in order to ensure that these resources were not depleted for clinical care providers. Competition for scarce resources disadvantaged students, who were considered less crucial for intraoperative or emergency patient care.

In specific recognition of the difficulties in learning resulting from low surgical volume and inadequate case mix, a majority of the students surveyed did not wish for the junior surgical clerkship to be continued at BDH. Qualitative focus group exploration of this theme shows that there was an appreciation for the value of the learning experience at BDH. Rather than completely relocating the curriculum to another center, students suggested that time spent at BDH could be supplemented by additional time spent at other hospitals in order to increase their breadth and depth of exposure. In particular, they suggested locations that would add the valuable experience of other surgical subspecialties (pediatric surgery, urology, orthopedics, and gastro-intestinal general surgery).

With regards to professionalism, faculty members observed that most learners were perpetually not on time to the bus that transported them to and from the hospital, and late to bedside presentations and ward teaching engagements. This was addressed repeatedly, but no significant consequences were applied. This needs to be considered in the total development of UGHE learners. It was also observed that dressing for clinical engagements was often casual, and unprofessional. Since no pre-existing UGHE dress regulations were identified, it may be useful to address this at the level of the clinical division for uniformity across clerkships.

There is a need to streamline the approach to expedited licensing for visiting faculty so as to maximize their input to the training within their time in Rwanda. This will both help to reduce the clinical load of the local surgeons and ensure that visiting faculty can carry out hands-on teaching. All visiting faculty had an introductory video to UGHE, department of surgery, and the clerkship along with several orientation documents shared with them. This should be carried forward, and if possible, further orientation sessions should be held with all potential faculty to further orient them to the BDH context.

Clerkship SWOT Analysis

Strengths	Weaknesses
<p>Highly motivated students</p> <p>Resourceful visiting and local faculty</p> <p>Strong network of fellows</p> <p>Variety of partners</p> <p>Hybrid model of clerkship delivery</p> <p>Simulation resources</p> <p>Pre-training of senior faculty (Harvard-UGHE courses)</p> <p>BDH specialist surgeon perceived as a good educator</p> <p>BDH surgeon is motivated to teach.</p> <p>BDH staff are eager to teach</p> <p>Good relationship between the UGHE staff and BDH staff</p> <p>Good professional relationship between students and BDH staff</p> <p>Shortage of BDH staff gives students more room for involvement in patient care.</p> <p>Hospital supported by PIH</p> <p>Personalized patient care at BDH relative to other hospitals (food, hygiene, patient support) makes patients more relaxed and engaged with students</p> <p>Trajectory of BDH to becoming a teaching hospital</p> <p>Most staff are very supportive of integrating teaching into care</p> <p>Rural location of hospital (reduces student distraction)</p> <p>Strong administrative support</p> <p>A strong UGHE brand</p> <p>Experienced academic leadership (DVC as a surgeon, clinical division lead, Internal Medicine lead, Quality Center)</p>	<p>Low volume and variety of surgical cases</p> <p>Limited faculty</p> <p>Limited faculty supervision</p> <p>Clerkship objectives were unclear to students and BDH staff</p> <p>Poor timeliness of students</p> <p>Extended didactic student interactions beyond 5pm</p> <p>BDH staff did not know the baseline level of knowledge of the students</p> <p>BDH is short staffed</p> <p>Only 1 surgeon specialist at BDH</p> <p>Limitation in OR space (one reserved for obstetrics and gynecology cases)</p> <p>High staff workload interfering with teaching</p> <p>Too many students (5) in the OR and on the ward (10).</p> <p>Surgeries canceled or delayed due to resource limitations and supply chain challenges</p> <p>Recurrent supply chain issues at BDH reduces efficiency of patient care</p> <p>Hospital receives low volume of trauma patients and is not set up to effectively assess and manage patients with trauma (no CT scan, orthopedic surgeon etc)</p> <p>Limited laboratory investigations</p> <p>Delays in receiving investigation results as a barrier to care and learning</p> <p>Interesting and unique cases are often referred to other (referral) hospitals</p> <p>Some examples of poor teamwork between BDH staff were highlighted</p> <p>Inadequate number of hospital scrubs affecting students ability to assist or observe surgeries</p> <p>Some BDH staff were unapproachable</p> <p>Initial reluctance of certain staff to teach students</p> <p>Students missed some lectures while they were in the OR</p> <p>Wednesday as a non-clinical day despite OR opportunities</p> <p>Absence of a formalized clinical teaching program in the afternoons</p> <p>Lack of study space for students within the hospital</p> <p>Single OPD- no space for students to clerk out-patients</p>

Opportunities	Threats
BDH hospital structure expansion project	Accommodating more students potentially places further strain on the system and will amplify weaknesses and challenges (e.g. having individuals from Junior and Senior Clerkships concurrently in the limited OR space).
Support from the ministry of health to becoming a teaching hospital	Potential of graduating breast cancer focused general practitioners with limited exposure to trauma and other aspects of surgical care.
Current status of BDH as a Cancer Center for Excellence	Overdependence on simulation as against actual patient contacts
High interest in UGHE by volunteers	Potential inability of students to meet required entrustable professional activities 18, 19, 20,22 and 23 (which deal with performance of minor cases including hernias, appendectomies, and observation of a wide variety of major cases) due to poor case mix and low surgical volume.
Potential international partnerships	Loss of access to a clinical teaching facility in proximity to UGHE
Potential local partnerships	Burnout of current surgical faculty (BDH and UGHE)
Expressed interest in facilitating surgical rotation by kinyarwanda speaking faculty from other hospitals	
Young GPs at BDH who are very eager to teach the students and can improve with some training	
Contacts at other potential facilities that can host future iterations of the clerkship	
Expanding online and on-campus library with sufficient learning resources	
Virtual Reality potential with partners like Allm, Proximie etc	
Ability to supply student scrubs and consumables (gloves, lubricating gel)	

6.0 CHALLENGES, PROPOSED SOLUTIONS AND SPECIFIC RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FUTURE SURGICAL ROTATIONS

Challenges	Proposed solutions
Challenges on Hospital-level organization/Number of Specialists	
Bed space for surgical patients is severely limited, and this limits the number of surgeries possible. This has a limiting effect on the volume of patients that students can interact with.	Expansion of hospital surgical bedspace.
The presence of only 1 hospital General Surgeon is a capacity limitation to both teaching and surgical service provision.	Support from our visiting faculty has given a positive boost to helping expand services to some degree, but the presence of an additional surgeon will be essential support to service expansion.
Insufficient surgical providers posted to the surgical ward.	Encourage hire of surgical faculty, and trained perioperative/ surgical nurses
Relatively high turnover of general practitioners and surgical nurses	Encourage stability by maintaining dedicated GPs on the surgery service
Limitation in OR space (only 1 staffed OR available for surgery; second OR is maintained for Obstetrics and Gynecology)	Infrastructural expansion with inclusion of more ORs so as to create space for visiting surgeons and fellows to operate. This will reduce patient wait times and clear up the backlog of patients on the surgery waiting list.

Low volume and variety of surgical cases coupled with significant case delays and cancellations due to resource limitations and supply chain challenges	Mitigation of supply chain challenges at a hospital administration level. Deliberate patient selection for non-breast oncologic surgeries, and expansion of OR space. The backlog of cases potentially guarantees good volume, but facility limitations have to be addressed to permit sufficient diverse case mix and sufficient case volumes.
Limited portfolio of investigations	Prioritize additions of culture and sensitivity and CT scans to BDH investigation portfolio. Public-private partnership might be a consideration.
Delays in receiving investigation results as a barrier to care and learning	Consider a time limit policy for receiving patient results.
Direct referral from the general OPD of surgical patients before contact with surgery students-interesting and unique cases are often referred to other (referral) hospitals.	Streamline the OPD to ensure that surgical teams and students see the patients prior to transfer without increasing the patient wait times.
Lack of study space for students within the hospital	Create a dedicated student study space within BDH for learners, like a medical student library in partnership with UGHE.
No dedicated space for student clerking at the OPD- only 1 room available.	Identify or create space for students to clerk patients and assist with surgical patient evaluation. This will increase the speed of patient encounters (by ensuring that new patients history and examinations are performed prior to seeing the specialist)
Challenges in Hospital Facilitator Training	
Clerkship objectives were unclear to students and BDH staff	Create additional avenues for facilitator training.
BDH staff did not know the baseline level of knowledge of the students	BDH facilitator pre-clerkship training with translation into kinyarwanda (involving ward assistants, nurses, GPs, anesthesiologists and perioperative nurses).
Initial reluctance of certain staff to teach students.	Training of trainers
Challenges in UGHE Surgery Departmental Level Organization	
Limited faculty supervision	
Clerkship objectives were unclear to students	Improve pre-clerkship orientation- emphasizing competencies and objectives of clinical time at BDH. Reinforce this throughout the posting with a 2-weekly session
Clerkship objectives were unclear to BDH staff	Involve all cadres of BDH staff (nurses, support staff and anaesthesiologists)
Extended didactic/flipped classroom interactions beyond 5pm	Lecture start and stop times should be respected by faculty and visiting faculty
Inadequate number of hospital scrubs affecting students ability to assist or observe surgeries	Ensure the purchase of UGHE student scrubs, gowns, and clogs to reduce the burden on BDH resources.
Wednesday as a non-clinical day despite significant OR	Move non-clinical day to Friday

opportunities	
Absence of a formalized clinical teaching program in the afternoons	Move some clinical teaching to afternoons.
Student Level Challenges	
Poor timeliness of students	Include timeliness into the clerkship grading beyond faculty assessment. Repeated training on professionalism.
Lack of learner independence	Incorporate emphasis on the dynamics of clinical learning, methods of self-directed learning, and the difference between pre-clinical and clinical learning into the Introduction to Clinical Practice. Encourage learner independence to an appropriate degree. This may be handled with time, experience and exposure.
Students missed some lectures while they were in the OR	Ensure that students prioritize clinical engagements over didactics. Clerkship administrative teams should ensure lectures are recorded and posted on Canvas for learners.

6.1 Recommendations for BDH Partnership

- Continue the transformation of BDH into a teaching hospital
- Increase the number and specialities of BDH surgeons.
- Complete the much needed expansion of infrastructure and space (with specific reference to the Operating rooms, surgical wards and the surgery outpatient departments) to accommodate an increasing number of students.
- Expand the surgical bedspace at BDH
- Adjust outpatient department clinical flow, such that surgery students have access to all surgical patients prior to referral.
- Adjust the GP schedule to facilitate presence and continuity on the surgical wards; the presence of 3 dedicated GPs in the surgical service would strengthen accompaniment significantly.
- Address supply chain challenges (medication, disposables etc)
- Lead a system-wide surgical quality improvement initiative in partnership with UGHE to identify system challenges and proffer potential solutions.

6.2 Recommendations for UGHE

- Consider use of additional or alternative clerkship sites to improve student exposure to a larger variety and higher volume of surgeries. This could be in the form of referral hospitals or complementary district hospitals with emphasis on trauma, gastrointestinal care etc.
- Adjust surgery schedule to free up Wednesday mornings for clinical activity
- Ensure logbooks are submitted 2-weekly to permit consistent formative feedback
- Enhance clarity of student and BDH staff expectations through pre-clerkship training workshops and continuous engagements
- Repeatedly emphasize the value of reading of course details (syllabus) iteratively to learners
- Emphasize the use of textbooks as reference at the start of the clerkship.
- Improve facilitation of visiting surgeon licenses to ensure that clinical activity is maximized to support the attending surgeon.

- Increase number of UGHE preceptors (possibly GPs) to permit full accompaniment through the clinical day
- Continue to lean on simulation and explore virtual reality/telesurgery options to increase student exposures to local, regional and international surgeries
- Introduce an emphasis on student-led learning and professionalism (including timeliness) into the Introduction to Practice of Medicine course

7.0 DISTRICT HOSPITAL CLINICAL CLERKSHIP FRAMEWORK

The experience of the inaugural surgical clerkship held at a district hospital in rural Rwanda can provide generalizable lessons for similar programs embedded in rural contexts. From the above observations, we have designed a framework for successful clinical undergraduate surgical curriculum delivery at the district hospital level.

Recommendation	Reasoning	Importance
Clerkship implemented across multiple sites	Ensure adequate breadth and depth of patient case exposure	Ensures adequate case mix and complementary surgical volume
Designated faculty per site and per clerkship location (without heavy clinical workload). A preceptor-student accompaniment model.	Ensure adequate student learning support in view of absence of senior trainee support network on site	Increases student satisfaction and enhances learning in the absence of a robust clinical care team or residency program ¹⁵ .
Introductory workshop for clerkship students	Ensure clear communication of the new clinical environment, roles, and expectations prior to commencement of the placement. Ensure students know their objectives and are introduced to their placement site.	Essential for smooth transition from a preclinical to a clinical environment, and
Introductory workshop for hospital staff (all cadres)	Ensure clear communication of people, roles, and expectations prior to commencement of the placement. Ensure that the hospital staff have embraced the integration of teaching responsibilities into clinical care, are aware of the personal and hospital system-wide benefits, and that misconceptions are mitigated. Ensure hospital staff know the clerkship objectives and are introduced to university faculty and preceptors	Essential for smooth transition from a non-teaching to a teaching district hospital and for adequate staff motivation.
Mid-term information workshop / team building initiatives for both hospital and university faculty	Facilitate ongoing open communication and troubleshooting	Key to handling any solvable or perpetual challenges during the clerkships. Contributes to a positive learning

		environment for the students.
Infrastructural support (E.g. supply of reusable and single use equipment primarily used by students including gloves and scrubs)	Avoid exacerbation of supply chain issues and stock-outs affecting patient care and students' learning.	Important to mitigating exclusion of students from learning due to solvable challenges with consumables and infrastructure. Reduces burden on limited hospital resources while creating a sense of support and involvement. Positively affects the learner's psyche, as a token of reducing burden on the hospital and patient care.
Clinical care support from university faculty	Mitigate potential workforce constraints experienced in district level hospitals and facilitate up-skilling of clinical staff	Helps with integrating both university and hospital faculty, and improving clinical care.
Exploration of reimbursement for clinical staff (not necessarily financial eg Continuing Professional Development points for courses attended etc)	Facilitate goodwill amongst clinical staff and engagement in teaching and training	Essential for hospital staff motivation.
In-house clinical training of clinical staff eg GPs and nursing staff	Facilitate goodwill amongst clinical staff Ensure students are exposed to appropriate, up-to-date standard of care	Will increase capacity for clinical teaching and contribute to continuing medical education of hospital facilitators.
Provide medical education training and mentorship for clinical staff	Empower clinical staff in their new roles as clinical educators. Ensure quality of clinical education as high a standard as possible.	Key to raising the standards of medical education in the district hospital setting, and enhancing the integration of teaching into care.
Periodic hospital operative and out patient log review	Identify challenges in patient volume and case mix early	Important for early detection and mitigation of skew of cases and challenges of low volume. This will help guide surgical system changes, and appropriate case selection for a robust educational exposure.
Mid-term student logbook review	Identify and address areas of shortfall in terms of students' exposure to adequate patient volume or variety	Will help the faculty to assess students' progress and provide feedback to student

Employment of a student advisor and provision of regular office hours	Ensure students have a point contact for academic or personal concerning in view of absence of usual senior trainee support network	Students will have a person to turn to for advice about their educational and personal lives.
Provide on-site study space dedicated for student use	Allow students to utilize the space for self-directed book-based learning during times when clinical learning opportunities are low	Students will be able to maximize their time and learning during clinical attachments
Streamline the acquisition of license to practice certification for visiting faculty	Ensure visiting faculty are able to maximize their time spent on-site in clinical areas	This will help reduce clinical workload for local clinicians whilst also providing more 'hands-on' teaching for students

8.0 CONCLUSION

It is heartening that the clerkship was successfully concluded, and most clerkship learning objectives were achieved by the students. No student in this 30 student cohort scored less than a C+ grade. This inaugural set of UGHE students were immersed in a novel clerkship site at BDH which was a rural hospital at the district hospital tier with a focus on cancer care.

A number of challenges were encountered, and possible solutions have been suggested in the hope that the learning experience of future cohorts will improve. Most students do not advise that the clerkship be continued at BDH due to low surgical volume and inadequate case mix, but this can be addressed by expanding the clerkship to additional sites and strengthening the surgical workforce (numbers and expertise) at the hospital.

UGHE is committed to contributing to the capacity of BDH to stand (eventually alone) as a training hub for both undergraduate and postgraduate surgery, and will contribute to the realization of this ideal. In the meantime, mitigation strategies need to be put in place by both UGHE and BDH stakeholders to ensure that the quality of ongoing surgical education is up to the desired standards.

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Appendix 1

2. Instructional Staff

Course Director*	Prof Robert Riviello RR	rriviello@bwh.harvard.edu
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Faculty/Dean*	Prof Abebe Bekele AB	dean@ughe.org
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Administrator of Center for Equity in Global Surgery	Dr Jules Iradukunda JI	jiradukunda@ughe.org

*Were in-person for all or part of their engagements

Yellow color code for facilitators of first cohort only 21

Orange color code for facilitators of second cohort only 23

White color code for facilitators of both cohorts

Appendix 2: List of Topics Covered in Surg 301

Informed Consent, Surgical Time Out, WHO SAFE SURGERY CHECKLIST, Patient Positioning, Patient Draping, History of Surgery, Introduction to Surgical Equipment Handling Safety and Choice, Use of local anesthesia, Suturing, Working with the GlobalSurgBox, Introduction to Global Surgery, Drainage of superficial abscess, Debridement of a contaminated wound, Excision of a cutaneous lesion, Punch, incision and excision biopsies, Wound dressing, Neuroendocrine response to trauma, Surgical safety, Primary and secondary trauma assessment, Resuscitation with basic life support, Resuscitation with advanced life support, Emphasis on securing of airway (ET intubation), Basics of ultrasound/introduction to FAST, Understanding wound healing, Nutritional optimisation, Intubation, Surgical sepsis and infection, Fluid optimisation of the surgical patient, Pediatric surgery I: Neonatal malformations, Imaging in Surgery, Pediatric surgery II: Acute abdomen in children Pediatric surgery III: Groin swellings in children Shock Responding to Common Perioperative Problems (e.g., fever, tachycardia, chest pain, bleeding) Pediatric surgery IV: Neck masses in children Use of Antibiotics in surgery Venous Access (Peripheral and Central) Peritonitis and Abdominal pain Abdominal mass Acute abdomen: Intestinal obstruction Acute abdomen: acute appendicitis Acute abdomen: acute pancreatitis and acute cholecystitis Lumps in groin (hernias and hydrocoele) Intestinal perforations Simulation: Intestinal obstruction case scenario Passing of nasogastric tubes Peptic ulcer disease Surgical Jaundice I: (General Approach to Surgical Jaundice) Surgical Jaundice II: (Management of Periampullary cancers, and Stone diseases in the gall bladder and CBD) CBCL: Upper GI bleeding Colon cancer Lower GI bleeding Rectal examinations Proctoscopy Sigmoid volvulus and colonic diverticula Perianal conditions Breast cancer Benign Breast lumps and infections Breast and axillary Examination/ biopsies Approach to the patient with hematuria Urinary retention and urethral stricture Prostatic disease: BPH and cancer/tumors of the urogenital system Stone diseases: Kidney, bladder and ureter Urinary tract surgical infections: Pyonephrosis, TB, peri-renal abscesses Leg and foot Ulceration (DM foot, TB, Ainhum etc) Male and Female urethral catheterization Suprapubic Catheterization Cleft lip and palate Difficulty swallowing: Achalasia and Esophageal cancer Approach to the burn patient Tumours of the skin Approach to the trauma patient I Orthopedic surgery I: Introduction to fractures and dislocation Burn patient assessment and management. Orthopedic surgery II: Upper limb Orthopedic surgery III: Lower limb (Femur and Tibia) Orthopedic surgery IV: Pelvis and Spine (Spinal Cord Injury) Orthopedic surgery V: Osteoarthritis Orthopedic surgery VI: Joint infections (septic arthritis) Bone tumors (benign and malignant) Splinting and POP application Thoracic trauma I Thoracic Trauma II Thoracic infections I: Thoracic empyema Approach to the neurosurgical patient Head injury Head trauma simulations/ Application of Neck Collar

SURGERY CLINICAL ROTATION EVALUATION FORM

Number Surgeries Scrubbed-In _____ **Number of surgeries Observed** _____

Name _____ **Period of Rotation** _____

Directions: Please take a moment to assess the clinical rotation using the following scale:

1-UNSATISFACTORY 2-SATISFACTORY 3-GOOD 4-EXCELLENT N/A-NOT APPLICABLE

Organization:

- Clinical duties were presented and discussed at the start of the rotation 1 2 3 4 N/A
- Educational goals were presented and discussed at the start of the rotation 1 2 3 4 N/A
- Evaluation process was presented and discussed at the start of the rotation 1 2 3 4 N/A
- Daily Schedule for patient care and teaching was structured efficiently 1 2 3 4 N/A
- Other healthcare professionals on the team were well integrated into patient care and teaching activities 1 2 3 4 N/A

Butaro District Hospital Faculty Leadership and Role Modeling:

- Demonstrated good 'bedside manner' and positive interpersonal communication skills with patients, family members and staff 1 2 3 4 N/A
- Treated each team member in a courteous and respectful manner 1 2 3 4 N/A
- Was usually prompt for teaching assignments; was always available and Accessible as a supervisor 1 2 3 4 N/A
- Showed respect for physicians in other specialties/subspecialties and for Other health professionals 1 2 3 4 N/A
- Recognized own limitations and used these situations as opportunities To demonstrate how he/she learns in order to keep up-to-date 1 2 3 4 N/A

UGHE Faculty Leadership and Role Modeling:

- Demonstrated good 'bedside manner' and positive interpersonal communication skills with patients, family members and staff 1 2 3 4 N/A
- Treated each team member in a courteous and respectful manner 1 2 3 4 N/A
- Was usually prompt for teaching assignments; was always available and Accessible as a supervisor 1 2 3 4 N/A
- Showed respect for physicians in other specialties/subspecialties and for Other health professionals 1 2 3 4 N/A
- Recognized own limitations and used these situations as opportunities To demonstrate how he/she learns in order to keep up-to-date 1 2 3 4 N/A

Patient Care-Operating Room

- Patient volume was sufficient for educational goals and objectives 1 2 3 4 N/A
- Variety of patient problems provided adequate learning experiences 1 2 3 4 N/A
- Opportunity to perform and/or assist in surgeries were sufficient to achieve Learning objectives 1 2 3 4 N/A
- Patient management was discussed regarding both resource limited and Resource rich settings 1 2 3 4 N/A
- I felt able to contribute to patient care effectively Yes No

Explain: _____

Patient Care-Ward

-Patient volume was sufficient for educational goals and objectives	1	2	3	4	N/A
-Variety of patient problems provided adequate learning experiences	1	2	3	4	N/A
-Opportunity to present patients and perform care were sufficient to achieve Learning objectives	1	2	3	4	N/A
-Patient management was discussed regarding both resource limited and Resource rich settings	1	2	3	4	N/A
-I felt able to contribute to patient care effectively	Yes	No			
Explain: _____					

Patient Care-Clinic

-Patient volume was sufficient for educational goals and objectives	1	2	3	4	N/A
-Variety of patient problems provided adequate learning experiences	1	2	3	4	N/A
-Opportunity to present patients were sufficient to achieve Learning objectives	1	2	3	4	N/A
-Patient management was discussed regarding both resource limited and Resource rich settings	1	2	3	4	N/A
-I felt able to contribute to patient care effectively	Yes	No			
Explain: _____					

Patient Care-Emergency Department

-Patient volume was sufficient for educational goals and objectives	1	2	3	4	N/A
-Variety of patient problems provided adequate learning experiences	1	2	3	4	N/A
-Opportunity to perform and/or assist in procedures were sufficient to achieve Learning objectives	1	2	3	4	N/A
-Patient management was discussed regarding both resource limited and Resource rich settings	1	2	3	4	N/A
-Opportunity to independently assess and present emergency patients	1	2	3	4	N/A
-I felt able to contribute to patient care effectively	Yes	No			
Explain: _____					

Patient Care Teaching-General Practitioners

-Devoted an appropriate amount of time to discussing patients and patient care decisions	1	2	3	4	N/A
-Observed my clinical and/or surgical skills and provided instructive Feedback and guidance	1	2	3	4	N/A
-Clearly communicated their thoughts and ideas, and allowed me to exercise My clinical judgment	1	2	3	4	N/A
-Used Relevant medical and/or scientific literature to support clinical decisions	1	2	3	4	N/A
-Patient care discussions integrated the social and ethical aspects of medicine (e.g. cost-containment, pain control, patients' rights, and humanism)	1	2	3	4	N/A
-The quality and amount of supervision and teaching provided was adequate	1	2	3	4	N/A

Patient Care Teaching-UGHE faculty

-Devoted an appropriate amount of time to discussing patients and patient care decisions	1	2	3	4	N/A
-Observed my clinical and/or surgical skills and provided instructive Feedback and guidance	1	2	3	4	N/A
-Clearly communicated their thoughts and ideas, and allowed me to exercise My clinical judgment	1	2	3	4	N/A
-Used Relevant medical and/or scientific literature to support clinical decisions	1	2	3	4	N/A
-Patient care discussions integrated the social and ethical aspects of medicine (e.g. cost-containment, pain control, patients' rights, and humanism)	1	2	3	4	N/A
-The quality and amount of supervision and teaching provided was adequate	1	2	3	4	N/A

Didactic (Classroom) Instruction

-Faculty gave well-organized lecture presentations that included opportunities For questions and discussion	1	2	3	4	N/A
-Faculty provided references, articles or other materials that stimulated me To research and review pertinent topics and patient problems	1	2	3	4	N/A

Evaluation and Feedback

-My overall performance was reviewed during the rotation pointing out My strengths and areas for improvement	1	2	3	4	N/A
-Faculty members demonstrated 'fairness' of comments during morning report Explaining reasons for my evaluation and allowing me to respond	1	2	3	4	N/A
-Faculty members demonstrated 'fairness' of comments during mini-CEX Explaining reasons for my evaluation and allowing me to respond	1	2	3	4	N/A
-Faculty members demonstrated 'fairness' of comments during case report Reviews explaining reasons for my evaluation and allowing me to respond	1	2	3	4	N/A

OVERALL, I WOULD RATE THIS CLINICAL ROTATION AS:

POOR (No Benefit)	FAIR (Little Benefit)	VERY GOOD (Beneficial)	EXCELLENT (Very Beneficial)
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Would you recommend that this rotation be continued in this hospital?	Yes	No
Would you recommend the faculty member (s) continue in this program?	Yes	No

COMMENTS, COMMENDATIONS, OR CONCERNS

Appendix 4

SURGERY CLINICAL ROTATION EVALUATION FORM

Name _____ Role _____

Clinical area _____

Directions: Please take a moment to assess the UGHE medical student clinical rotations:

1-Strongly agree 2-Somewhat agree 3-Neutral 4-Somewhat disagree 5-Strongly disagree

Concerning medical students:

- I felt qualified to help in teaching and training the surgery medical students

1 2 3 4 5

- I felt that I had enough time during my working day to help teach and train the medical students

1 2 3 4 5

- I enjoyed teaching and training the surgery medical students

1 2 3 4 5

- I felt confident with regards to how medical students should be spending their time on a day-to-day basis during their hospital placement

1 2 3 4 5

- The medical students treated me with respect

1 2 3 4 5

- I felt having the medical students in the hospital contributed positively to the quality of patient care

1 2 3 4 5

- I would welcome medical students on their surgery rotation back to Butaro District Hospital in the future

1 2 3 4 5

Please provide any general comments or concerns regarding the medical students

Concerning UGHE faculty:

- Communication was clear from UGHE faculty regarding expectations from me prior to the start of the medical student rotation

1 2 3 4 5

- I felt the UGHE faculty were friendly and approachable

1 2 3 4 5

- I felt the UGHE faculty were helpful in teaching and training the medical students

1 2 3 4 5

- UGHE faculty treated me with respect

1 2 3 4 5

- I felt able to discuss with UGHE faculty if I had any concerns regarding a medical students conduct

1 2 3 4 5

- I felt able to discuss with UGHE faculty if I had any concern regarding patient welfare

1 2 3 4 5

- I felt having the UGHE faculty in the hospital contributed positively to the quality of patient care

1 2 3 4 5

Please provide any general comments or concerns regarding the medical students

Concerning Butaro District Hospital as a learning environment:

- Patient volume at BDH is sufficient for teaching and training medical students

1 2 3 4 5

- Patient case mix at BDH is sufficient for teaching and training medical students

1 2 3 4 5

- Workforce capacity at BDH sufficient for teaching and training medical students

1 2 3 4 5

- I believe that Butaro District Hospital provided a good learning environment for the surgery medical students

1 2 3 4 5

Please provide any general comments or concerns regarding Butaro District Hospital as a learning environment for the medical students

Overall, I would rate this clinical rotation as:

Poor Fair Good Very Good Excellent

Would you recommend that this rotation be continued at this hospital? Yes No

Would you recommend the faculty member (s) continue in this program? Yes No

Please provide any additional final comments or concerns regarding the surgery medical student attachment
